

D4.22 Third periodic report on JIPs

WP4 Joint Integrative Projects

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1. Introduction

The joint core mission of partners in the One Health EJP is to provide expertise and services to prevent, detect and respond to societal challenges such as foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats shared by people and animals. The chain of actions from prevention via detection to response defines a series of capacities that need to be maintained and kept up to date by these expert institutes. These pertain to their capacity to design and implement surveillance activities, develop high quality laboratory methods, access relevant reference materials and data, as well as to their ability to interpret and communicate surveillance information in a timely and appropriate manner, as well as to provide guidance to risk managers about relevant actions, both for prevention and response. Similarly, the purpose of integrative activities and projects within the OHEJP is to strengthen the joint preparedness of partners to prevent, detect and respond to hazards within their joint remit, both nationally and in collaboration within other EU institutes and -agencies. Due to the legislated landscape in which OHEJP partners operate, and as a result of the close relationship and collaboration with the key EU stakeholders of OHEJP, ECDC and EFSA, there are already many strategies, initiatives, activities and systems in place to develop the capacity to respond to joint hazards within the field of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats.

The objective of Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) is not to replicate, but to strengthen existing, well-functioning systems. The guidance and insight of EFSA and ECDC is of major importance to help such alignment. The objective of JIPs is also to bridge the gap between the sectors by successively focusing on the inter-sectorial mechanisms along the chain from preparedness to response, and to investigate and improve how the work processes of microbiologists, epidemiologists, and information specialists, function across the Public Health/Animal Health/Food Safety interface at the national level. Strengthening of inter-sectorial mechanisms at the national level will subsequently benefit the supra-national level.

Consequently, the ambition of the integrative activities of the One Health EJP is to develop structures, work processes and platforms that bridge inter-sectorial division within the domains defined by the OHEJP scope, resulting in one European surveillance community. This integrative development should be aligned with European priorities, accommodate, and be adapted to existing EU initiatives and support long-term sustainability in the improved joint capacity. Operational integration is promoted by means of several different instruments, the primary instrument being the implementation of JIPs. Prioritised needs regarding joint collaborative resources were identified in the strategic research agenda (SRA), developed in the context of the EJP proposal. An integrative strategy matrix was developed where the domains Foodborne zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats became the three pillars of the OHEJP. Further, the components that contribute to the improvement of the “Prevent, Detect and Respond chain” were identified. The prioritised components are reflected in the Joint Integrative Projects, which correspond to each of these components.

The JIPs were selected in the two internal calls of the OHEJP. The first two JIPs, ORION and COHESIVE, started in 2018. ORION focuses on the semantic and technical interoperability between the sectors, with focus on surveillance information. COHESIVE focuses on the ability to pick up, share and communicate signals as well as the ability to conduct joint risk assessments.

In 2020, three new JIPs started. MATRIX aims to extend the efforts of COHESIVE and ORION and to advance the implementation of One Health surveillance in practice, by building on existing resources, adding value to them, and creating synergies among the sectors. OH-Harmony-CAP aims to collect information on current capabilities, capacities, and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory and the primary diagnostic level. CARE will focus on developing new One Health concepts for proficiency testing of laboratories, reference materials and quality/availability of demographic data. The three JIPs had their kick-off meetings in the beginning of 2020, before the coronavirus pandemic hit the world. At these meetings, the WP4 leader got the opportunity to present the OHEJP process.

The topic “Sharing best intervention practice – twinning and simulation exercises” relating to the sixth component “Action” in the chart did not attract any applications in the second call. During year 3 two new activities in line with this topic were initiated. A new JIP proposal “COVRIN” targeting *SARS-CoV2 Research Integration & Preparedness* was prepared and discussed with REA. After some modifications of the project plan the proposal was approved and the project prepared to start in March 2021. In parallel, a prioritisation of new joint integrative activities was done by the SSB and it was decided that a simulation exercise should be carried out within the OHEJP. This exercise will be executed on a national level. Planning starts during year 4.

Since the joint EU capacity is a function of each member state’s capacity, the JIPs are expected to make their developments accessible to all partners and ensure there is transfer of skills and knowledge and promote harmonised approaches wherever it is relevant. In this way, the JIPs will serve to strengthen the scientific capacity within the EJP, as well as the future prevention, preparedness, detection and response of the EU to foodborne and other emerging threats across human-animal-environmental sectors. To do this the projects have been encouraged to disseminate results and outcomes in various ways. Among the initiatives within the JIPs are for instance several national ongoing pilots to harmonize the work between public and animal health and food safety authorities. There are also supra national pilots, where new tools are implemented at EFSA and ECDC by project members spending some time at each institute. Other tools developed by the JIPs are integrated into already existing tools like the FoodChain Lab.

WP4 is responsible for the supervision and evaluation of the JIPs. The body of this report is based on the 12-month reports for year 3 provided by the five projects, with an initial introductory chapter summarising their operational performance in year 3.

2. Summary of the performance of the Joint Integrative Projects

2.1. Milestones and deliverables

The five JIPs planned to submit 27 deliverables in Y3 (see table below). At the time of writing this report, 81% of the planned deliverables were finalized and uploaded on the private area of the OHEJP Website. Some deliverables still need to be uploaded on Zenodo. The impacts of COVID-19 were mentioned as the main reason for delay of deliverables. For the first call projects, ORION and COHESIVE, all the deliverables for the end of Y3 were extended to M42 due to the 6-month extension of the projects.

JIP	No. of deliverables Y3	No. of finalized deliverables Y3	No. of delayed deliverables Y3
ORION	0	0	0
COHESIVE	10	7	3
CARE	11	9	2
OH-HARMONY-CAP	4	4	0
MATRIX	2	2	0
Total	27	22	5
Percentage	-	81%	19%

In total the JIPs had listed 23 milestones for Y3 (see table below), whereof 87% were achieved on time. The impacts of COVID-19 were mentioned as the main reason for delay of milestones.

JIP	No. of milestones Y3	No. of finalized milestones Y3	No. of delayed milestones Y3
ORION	0	0	0
COHESIVE	6	6	0
CARE	12	10	2
OH-HARMONY-CAP	4	4	0
MATRIX	1	0	1
Total	23	20	3
Percentage	-	87%	13%

Actions resulting from the follow up of milestones and deliverables:

- There are regular meetings between the WP4 support team and the JIP Project leaders (PLs) to inform about upcoming events, reports to be written etc., but also to share experiences.
- The PLs are reminded about upcoming deliverables about one month before each date for delivery.
- The WP4 team checks the delivery of each project deliverable and that it is uploaded correctly. WP4 have provided guidance on how to do this.
- WP4 takes care of the dissemination of deliverables to stakeholders indicated by the PLs.
- All PLs have been asked to make plans for how effects of the pandemic will be handled.
- The Scientific Publication Policy has been updated to make the scope of it clearer and the routines easier to follow.

2.2. Publications

As the integrative projects are more development-oriented and a natural part of the alignment process, scientific publications are not an expected major outcome of the projects. Publications in scientific peer-reviewed journals 2020 as well as other published outcomes are listed below.

2.2.1. Peer-reviewed scientific papers

Houe, H. et al. (2020). Opportunities for Improved Disease Surveillance and Control by Use of Integrated Data on Animal and Human Health. *Frontiers in Veterinary Medicine*, 6: 301, pp. 1-8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00301> Gold open access. <https://zenodo.org/record/4269579#.YGNAI0BuKsc>

Joensen, KG. et al. (2020). Whole-Genome Sequencing to Detect Numerous *Campylobacter jejuni* Outbreaks and Match Patient Isolates to Sources, Denmark, 2015–2017. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 26(3), 523-532. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid2603.190947> Gold open access. <https://zenodo.org/record/4269536#.YGNA1kBuKsc>

Filter, M. et al. One Health Surveillance Codex: promoting the adoption of One Health solutions within and across European countries. Accepted for publication in the journal “One Health”. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100233>. Gold open access.

2.2.2. Other published outcomes except meeting reports

- Korsgaard, H. B. et al. (2020). DANMAP 2019 - Use of antimicrobial agents and occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria from food animals, food and humans in Denmark. Statens Serum Institut og Technical University of Denmark. www.danmap.org
- Swedish reports on “Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans 2019” (2020). www.sva.se
- One dataset compiling all surveillance data available in the reports, including surveillance methods annotated according to the OH-CRAC principles¹ developed in ORION (consensus report annotation checklist), was also published in the Swedish data portal in both human readable format (comma separated values, CSV) and machine-readable format (RDF). The latter is explicitly annotated with machine readable surveillance concepts from the Health Surveillance Ontology. All permanent unique identifiers created are listed at: <http://datadrivensurveillance.org/campylobacter-surveillance-in-sweden/>
- A prototypic “Glossaryfication web service” was created that automatically identifies matching glossary terms in a user-defined document and in this way helps users to create document specific glossaries annexes. This will help to avoid misinterpretation of terms defined differently in certain OH sectors in the future and add value to the OHEJP Glossary. Not yet publicly available.

2.2.3. Meeting proceedings and abstracts

Sixteen conference proceedings and abstracts were published from the JIPs during year 3. See individual project 12 M reports for details.

2.3. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs, European, international and national projects

The aim of the JIPs is to generate integrative activities. In addition, OHEJP WP4 arranges cogwheel workshops to facilitate interactions between the JRPs/JIPs and other European projects and initiatives. Another initiative to facilitate interactions between the OHEJP projects are Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs). Some examples of interactions initiated by JIPs are provided here. Additional and more detailed information can be found in the technical reports.

¹ <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/5-the-dissemination-principle.html>

2.3.1. Interactions initiated by JIPs with international focus

During year 3, especially ORION and COHESIVE have continued the development of different tools that support and facilitate a harmonized work between authorities on the public health, food and animal health areas. The three JIPs that started in 2020 have initiated tasks in line with their project plans.

The dissemination of the outcomes from the JIPs is of vital importance to achieve impact within the relevant OH sectors. In October Y3 an OHEJP internal workshop was arranged with the objective to allow the OHEJP consortium to learn more about the tools and solutions developed by ORION. A report is available [here](#).

The OHEJP Glossary, developed by ORION in collaboration with COHESIVE and the JRP NOVA, has been completed with a new “Glossaryfication web service”. This tool allows to automatically find matches between a user-defined document and a set of online glossaries. In ORION an evaluation of resources from the OH Surveillance Codex (OHS Codex) was performed in collaboration with EFSA and ECDC. The first version of the OHS Surveillance Codex was publicly released and presented during ASM2020. The Codex is a guidance document that complies with and extends the “Tripartite Guide to Addressing Zoonotic Diseases in Countries”. Also, the OH-CRAC was extensively validated, improved and applied in several pilot applications. This tool supports harmonized reporting of surveillance meta-information in OH surveillance data reports. One improvement is a web-based service that supports the adoption of OH-CRAC by end-users. New web applications were also created to provide public access to the surveillance systems inventory (https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/EJPOrion_WP2Epi/) as well as the methods and tools inventory (<https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/toolsdatabase/>). New collaborations and information exchange with other EJP projects (e.g., MATRIX) or initiatives (e.g., RAKIP, BeONE, SISOT) have been initiated by ORION.

The online decision support tool, developed within COHESIVE, has been significantly improved and is available for OHEJP members. This tool helps the user to select the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The development of the tracing web portal - FoodChain-Lab Web – (FCL Web) has advanced further. A revised login procedure and data security documents have been developed and FCL Web is available in production mode.

In CARE there are several ongoing activities to identify available and existing External Quality Assurance (EQA) programs offered to the National Reference Laboratories. From this information a guidance will be set up for new EQA scheme expanding to whole genome sequencing (WGS). The partners have agreed on a list of nine pathogens, all known to be responsible for foodborne human infections, to serve as a basis for gaps to be identified in available reference material to cover all known serotypes, genotypes and generally pathogenic variants of the selected pathogens.

2.3.2. Interactions initiated by JIPs with national focus

ORION has continued to enrich the content of the web-based community NGS handbook and implemented the first cross-sector IRIDA (<https://www.irida.ca/>) NGS data analysis platform at the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (<https://www.nrec.no/>). During this process new functional NGS data analysis pipelines were created in collaboration with the IRIDA. Further, a generic template for evaluating impact and outcomes of each national pilot has been established in ORION. The national Integration pilots contributed to improved OH reporting, e.g., in the Salmonella chapter of the DANMAP 2019 report (<https://www.danmap.org/>). New processes with improved collaboration among the national OH sectors have also been established, which has led to a significantly improved

understanding on each other's sectors surveillance activities and results. Specifically, new instructions and guidelines were produced that will be used in future reporting practices.

In COHESIVE, a national core group has been established in three countries and a stakeholder analysis is performed. The main goal is to develop guidelines for national One Health systems or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary-food collaborations. A general European-level Q-fever surveillance map has been made in COHESIVE and potential improvements for surveillance have been identified, which will be highlighted to animal health surveillance colleagues in England, since the UK was chosen to be retrospectively analyzed.

In OH-HARMONY CAP an OHLabCap instrument will be developed, which will support harmonised data collection and validation on selected food borne pathogens and encourage cross-sectorial communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthening national networks. The MATRIX project is advancing the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice by building onto existing resources, adding value and creating synergies among the sectors at a national level. The development of dashboards that enable data-driven surveillance to be carried out as an inter-sectorial activity, is one main activity, which is initiated in Sweden and Norway.

2.3.3. Cogwheel Workshops

The OHEJP WP4 is responsible for the arrangement of Cogwheel Workshops. The purpose of these workshops is to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. The JIPs have been presented and introduced to external European H2020 projects in these workshops. During year 3 there have been three Cogwheel Workshops.

In January 2020, the fourth cogwheel workshop was arranged, targeting the EU project InfAct (Information for Action). A total of 40 partners and 28 countries are involved in the project, aiming at strengthening national and EU health information systems by establishing a sustainable research infrastructure; by strengthening European health information and knowledge bases to reduce health information inequalities and by supporting health information interoperability and innovative health information tools and data sources. The JIPs ORION and MATRIX participated in the workshop.

The fifth cogwheel workshop was arranged in April 2020, targeting five projects funded through the 9th call from the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPIAMR) on diagnostics and surveillance; MAGITICS (machine learning for digital diagnostics of antimicrobial resistance), K-STaR (a K-mer-based approach for institutional antimicrobial resistance surveillance, transmission monitoring, and rapid diagnostics), OASIS (One Health antimicrobial resistance surveillance through innovative sampling), TRIuMPH (improving the tricycle protocol: upscaling to national monitoring, detection of CPE and WGS pipelines for One Health Surveillance) and IDx (an exploration of regulatory, corporate, relational, and technical barriers to uptake of diagnostics in the fight against antimicrobial resistance). Seven OHEJP and the five invited JPIAMR projects signed up with presentations at the CW. Twelve OHEJP projects were represented in total, including the JIPs ORION, OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX.

The sixth cogwheel workshop was arranged in November 2020, targeting SafeConsume, which is a research and innovation action funded by Horizon 2020. It is a five-year project, in its fourth year. The consortium consists of 32 partners from 14 countries in Europe and is coordinated from Norway (Nofima). The overall objective of SafeConsume is to reduce health burden

from foodborne illness through changing consumer behaviour. To this workshop the OHEJP PhD students, the new partners of the OHEJP enlargement effort and all OHEJP member institutes were invited. SafeConsume highlighted COHESIVE, NOVA, DiSCoVer, TOXOSOURCES, ADONIS, EnvDis and SUSTAIN to be of special interest and these projects were specifically encouraged to participate in the CW with SafeConsume. Six OHEJP projects signed up with presentations at the workshop including the JIPs ORION, COHESIVE and MATRIX. Seven OHEJP projects were represented in total, including two PhD projects. The workshop received positive feedback and good opportunities for future cooperation were identified.

2.3.4. Thematic Integrative Meetings

Thematic Integrative Meetings (TIMs) are annual digital workshops aiming to facilitate integration across the OHEJP domains, but within themes. The TIM organised in Y3 had the title “Practical use on NGS”. Two topics were addressed; Topic 1: Getting from raw NGS data to outbreak detection and Topic 2: The future roles of NGS data producers and data collectors/users. Among the speakers were Dr. Hanna Skarin, Director of EURL-Campylobacter, SVA, Uppsala, Sweden and Dr. Mirko Rossi, EFSA, Parma, Italy. The meeting attracted 79 participants. More information is to be found in D4.15 “*Report from thematic meeting II*”.

2.4. Data Management Plan (DMP)

ORION and COHESIVE have updated their DMPs. CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP and MATRIX have provided the first versions of their DMPs, using the template of the new CDP-tool, and received their first feedback from the WP4 support team.

2.5. Critical risks

The risks identified in the projects’ 12-month report are summarised in the table below.

Description of risk	ORION	COHESIVE	CARE	OH-HARMONY-CAP	MATRIX
Loss of keypersons (staff and/or leaders)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No	No	No	No	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No	No	No	No	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No	Yes	No	No	No
Other risks (please describe)	No	COVID	No	COVID	No

Critical risks that have been managed during Y3 are mainly due to the pandemic, which has caused delays. Especially COHESIVE has been affected, because many of their activities are optimally performed if people can meet physically. In this JIP many of the project members also have had to deal with COVID-19 related duties. Since COHESIVE was already delayed before, which is explained in

D4.17 Second periodic report on JIPs, the possibility for an extension was highly appreciated. COHESIVE has got an extension with 6 months and is expected to end in June 2021.

There are only minor delays in the other JIPs, but these are not expected to impact the final deliveries. The projects have adapted well to the new situation where digital meetings are the way to work. ORION has also got an extension with 6 months and will end in June 2021.

There have also been some changes of personnel in the projects, but this has not caused any major delays. There has been a change of project leaders in MATRIX and in OH-HARMONY-CAP.

Critical risks are discussed at the quarterly meetings with all the JIP leaders, as well as in individual follow-up meetings between WP4 support team and PLs.

2.6. Ethical Assessment

Ethical implications that have been identified are being managed. Regarding the issues raised by the ethical advisors on the ORION project that the applicants must confirm the compliance with GDPR and must specify whether human genome will be sequenced, ORION has verified the compliance with GDPR rules and has informed that no human genome will be sequenced in any of ORION's pilot studies. The ethical advisors have got satisfactory replies regarding the comments on the CARE project. A clarification is made by OH-HARMONY-CAP regarding health and safety procedures and that these are conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation and followed by the staff involved in the project. MATRIX has responded to the comments by the ethical advisors. Regarding the planned collaboration with St. Kitts, this has been cancelled because of the delay due to COVID, the tight time frame and required capacity, which neither partner could fulfil. This means that no information, documents, or any other material will be shared with St. Kitts. Matrix has also made it clear that no personal data will be collected as part of MATRIX.

3. JIP1 – ORION

3.1. Summary of the work carried out

The ORION project progressed successfully from the “Improvements and new resources” (2nd) phase into the “Evaluation” phase as described in the project proposal. This third phase encompassed the implementation of national One Health (OH) pilots as well as the continuous improvement of resources developed during the second phase.

In WP1 the evaluation of resources from the OH Surveillance Codex (OHS Codex) was performed in the WP1 national and the WP1 & WP3 supranational pilot with EFSA & ECDC. A first version of the OHS Codex was publicly released, presented during ASM2020 and a corresponding publication was submitted to the One Health journal. WP1 developed new resources that helped to maintain and exploit the OHEJP Glossary, e.g., a new “Glossaryfication web service”. This tool allows to automatically find matches between a user-defined document and a set of online glossaries. Also, the OH-CRAC was extensively validated, improved and applied in several pilot applications. A new web-based service was created that supports the adoption of OH-CRAC by end-users.

In WP2-Epi resources were invested into the preparation and implementation of national pilots. Some pilots were however affected by delays due to COVID-19 and staff fluctuations. The KnowledgeBase - Epi was significantly improved in Y3, from the content as well as from the technical side. Shiny web applications were created to provide public access to the user-friendly surveillance systems inventory (https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/EJPOrion_WP2Epi/) as well as the methods and tools inventory (<https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/toolsdatabase/>). WP2-NGS continued to enrich the content of the web-based community NGS handbook and successfully implemented the first cross-sector IRIDA (<https://www.irida.ca/>) NGS data analysis platform at the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (<https://www.nrec.no/>). During this process it was discovered that some of the original IRIDA pipelines were non-functioning, so additional resources were allocated towards creating new functional NGS data analysis pipelines in collaboration with the IRIDA project. WP2-Integration organized an ORION pilot integration workshop in January 2020 to synchronize the work done in the different country specific pilots under the overarching OHS Codex framework. A generic template for evaluating impact and outcomes of each pilot was established, as well as a strategy for how lessons learned from the individual pilots can be captured and communicated. The national WP2-Integration pilots contributed to improved OH reporting, e.g. in the Salmonella chapter of the DANMAP 2019 report (<https://www.danmap.org/>). The development work in WP3 focused on establishing the conceptual and technical foundations for innovative data interoperability solutions related to the linked open data concept. During the national WP3 pilot this concept was promoted and new processes with improved collaboration among the national OH sectors were established. This led to a significantly improved understanding on each other’s sectors surveillance activities and results. Specifically, new instructions and guidelines were produced that will be used in future reporting practices, which also pave the way for the application of data interoperability solutions developed by WP3.

The project organized trimonthly web meetings for the whole ORION consortium including stakeholders and interested EJP members, and monthly calls for the WP leaders & deputy leaders. The project contributed to the EJP DMP steering board, initiated new collaborations and information exchange with other EJP projects (e.g. MATRIX) or initiatives (e.g. RAKIP, BeONE, SISOT). Members of the ORION project presented research results at the ASM2020 and the 6th World One Health Congress. Several scientific publications were submitted or are in the final preparation phase. ORION organized an EJP internal Cogwheel workshop, and an online NGS workshop.

3.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1- OH Surveillance Codex

JIP1-WP1-T3: One Health pilot (M7-M39)

JIP01-WP1-T3-ST2: Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot (M13-M33)

- The WP1 OH Pilot were focussed on applying and improving two ORION solutions: the OHEJP Glossary (formerly ORION Glossary) and the One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC).
- In M25, an additional pilot called “EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC” was initiated. This pilot evaluated the applicability of the four solutions developed by WP1 (OHS Codex, OHEJP Glossary, OH-CRAC) and WP3 (Health Surveillance Ontology) in processes that generate information valuable in a One Health context by EFSA and ECDC. In this context, apart from the updates and developments on the aforementioned resources, a new web service was developed to facilitate the semi-automatic mapping of concepts from the EFSA’s catalogues into the new Health Surveillance Ontology (HSO) developed in WP3. This web service helps to create an easy to maintain link between the constantly evolving EFSA catalogues and HSO that can be exploited by future semantic search technologies and services that build on linked open data (LOD).

JIP1-WP1-T3-ST3: Execution of the OH pilot - applying the “OH Surveillance Codex” guide (M19-M42)

- For the WP1 OH Pilot, the EJP project “Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics” (ARDIG) and “German One Health Initiative” (GOHI) were chosen as use cases to validate the WP1 solutions in the AMR and AMU domains. During this third year, meetings with representatives of these projects in BfR have been organized to present the different resources and evaluate its practical applicability. In these meetings, we have mainly focused on improving the coverage and quality of AMR and AMU related terms within OHEJP Glossary, evaluated the usability of the Glossaryfication web service based on the OHEJP glossary and extended this tool with other glossaries meaningful in the AMR and AMU context. Further, the OH-CRAC checklist was validated with surveillance data reports provided by ARDIG and GOHI. The EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC incorporated a new research scientist at the beginning of this year. This pilot hosted monthly calls with EFSA & ECDC and validate the selected ORION solutions on EFSA & ECDC data on Salmonella, Campylobacter and AMR surveillance. ORION presented the findings from the WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot during EFSA’s 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses Monitoring Data on 19-20 October 2020.

JIP1-WP1-T4: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

- The first draft of “OH Surveillance Codex” was finalized by M24. During Y3, this resource was significantly improved, updated and a new version was implemented as an open source community resource that is available via <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>. In Y4, this OHS Codex will be further extended to include also the “lessons learned” summaries from pilot studies performed in the context of ORION. A collaboration plan was established with the EJP MATRIX project to further extend and maintain the OHS Codex once the ORION project ended.

- The OHEJP Glossary (publicly available in <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>) is the result of the collaborative effort of three EJP projects namely ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE, with support from OH experts of EJP stakeholders. Based on feedback received during application of the resource in several pilots we have focused on the maintenance of the OHEJP Glossary in Y3, which encompassed the continuous extension, curation and validation of the glossary content. This process was supported by the implementation of a new backend software infrastructure, which provides now efficient technical and operational resources to curate and manage the glossary content in a collaborative manner.
- As part of the newly started supranational pilot with EFSA & ECDC WP1 created a so-called “Glossaryfication web service”. This software provides benefit to the OHEJP Glossary as end users can now automatically search within any user-provided text document for terms that are contained in the OHEJP Glossary. Currently, this service is only accessible for users with login credentials as the web service is still under development. In addition to the OHEJP Glossary, other glossaries from national and international institutions were added to the Glossaryfication web service, so that these can also be used for creation of document-specific glossaries. Once all the feature requests from the different pilot applications and certain IT security constraints will be solved, the tool will be accessible without login request.
- The OH-CRAC supports the harmonized reporting of surveillance meta-information in future sector-specific or OHS data reports. The OH-CRAC gives recommendations on what meta-information should be provided and how to structure it within future surveillance data reports. During this year, we performed a joint analysis of existing cross-sectoral guidelines and frameworks that were mapped to OH-CRAC schema to support end-users in the checklist completion and we improved the provided sub-headings, definitions and added examples of linked metadata. This resource was made available as a web-based interactive annotation tool (<https://aflex.vrac.iastate.edu/checklist/?t=OH-CRAC>) for functional meta-information extraction in reports/documents uploaded as pdf files. The application of OH-CRAC in the WP1 pilots proofed that the adoption of OH-CRAC could improve the completeness and transparency of the surveillance data reports and facilitates the cross-sector mapping of meta-information on surveillance data.
- The work within the ORION WP1 and WP3 supra-national pilot is also focused on demonstrating the potential of using HSO to join different datasets and link them to other sources (e.g. EFSA, ECDC or wikidata). For this purpose, we have created different web services that make the data from these datasets interoperable by converting data from Excel format (csv, xls format) into the Resource Description Framework (RDF) format, which is a standard data exchange format that allows data exchange via the WWW. Once data has been converted into this machine-readable format it becomes findable and interoperable allowing also semantic search algorithms to automatically retrieve information. In Y4, it will be demonstrated that this way of data representation will help to enrich and link EFSA / ECDC data with data from other LoD sources.

WP2-Epi

JIP1-WP2-T2: Improving OH Knowledge Base – Epi (M13-M24)

- Multiple surveillance systems are carried out annually by Member States (MS) of the European Union in the sectors of public health, animal health and food & feed. Some results of these surveillance systems are reported to EFSA, ECDC, and/or other reporting systems

of the EU. However, several MS carry out additional national or regional surveillance related to food borne zoonoses that are not reported to higher EU reporting bodies. To get an overview of surveillance systems in existence across EU MS and to easily access and search for this information within a single platform, the aim of this work package was to develop a knowledge base for surveillance systems including an easy search platform with references to data sources.

- The framework for this OH Knowledge Base was developed (inventories) and an application server was set up at FLI to provide an easy data access and search platform.

JIP1-WP2-T2-ST1 - Data collection and integration

- To collect the data for the database, we first defined the scope of the data to be collected. For consistency we aligned, as closely as possible, the database scheme with that of EFSA and ECDC. The final tables were developed this year after consolidating all internal and external input. We started with the collection of the final datasets in M34. We also consolidated all data that was previously submitted to the FLI from project partners during the development of the final data tables into the final datasets. These consolidated data were sent to the submitting partners for validation before uploading to the public web platform (Shiny)
- The data collection was also discussed with EJP MATRIX. As they were very interested in analysing the data and proceeding with the data collection, a webinar was carried out in M31.
- Overall, final data collection was delayed due to missing personnel resources (the recruitment process was delayed by COVID 19).

JIP1-WP2-T2-ST2 - Data analysis and validation

- A data analysis model based on the item response theory (Rasch model) was adopted and tested with data from preliminary data collection. The Rasch model is used to quantify properties that cannot be ascertained directly but only indirectly, for example by means of questionnaires. The Rasch model is a probabilistic model with which latent variables are inferred. The success of the Rasch model is dependent on level of response to the questionnaire and subsequent volume of data. Although the model is developed, data analysis is delayed as the input data collection is not finished yet.
- A web application with a user interface was developed using R statistical software. In parallel, a public shiny app was setup at FLI (M30) and the software was tested. The web application was published in M33 at <https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/toolsdatabase/>

JIP1-WP2-T2-ST3 - Knowledge integration and Decision support

- In the OH context, we are dealing with a transdisciplinary process, and knowledge integration across the disciplines requires integration of two types of knowledge: the theoretical and abstract knowledge of the sciences (science) and the concrete and empirical knowledge of practice (practice). The integration of science and practice ensures that both political decisions are based on scientific knowledge and insights, and that questions of science are directed to decision-relevant aspects of practice. Given the fundamental uncertainties that run through the entire context of the OH approach, integration in the sense of mutual learning is necessary.

- Knowledge integration can support decision makers in evaluating existing surveillance systems and performing gap analyses. Furthermore, it can support decision makers in assessing data from other MS. Other EJP partners and projects (e.g. EJP Matrix) may use this data for further analysis and likely maintain the database after the end of EJP Orion.
- We aim to realise knowledge integration in the knowledge inventories, by listing the theoretical knowledge alongside the context in which the knowledge was generated. Links to literature and application examples are provided for this purpose.
- A database including a web application with a user interface was developed using R statistical software. The public shiny web application was setup at the FLI (M30) and the software was tested. The web application was published in M33 at https://shiny.fli.de/ife-apps/EJPOrion_WP2Epi/.
- Since publication, we have updated the server two times to improve usability and to add additional data. Data will be continually added and updated until the end of the project (see JIP1-WP2-T2-ST1).

JIP1-WP2-T3: Epi - OH pilot studies (M7-M39)

JIP1-WP2-T3-ST1: One Health Pilot 1: Toxoplasma gondii (carried out by FLI and BfR, Germany) (M7-M39)

- In this pilot study, we first analysed the available data on *T. gondii* surveillance in reports from the different sectors. We then carried out a narrative literature review on seroprevalence data and risk factors for infection with *T. gondii* in relevant livestock species. The study on the risk factors was published in January 2019 (Stelzer et al. 2019).
- A systematic review is now in progress to analyze the data collected in the narrative literature review. Due to a change in personnel and a delay in the recruitment process, the project was delayed and as a result, it was necessary to update the literature covered by the systematic review. In M33-M36, we revised the project plan, updated the extraction to include literature from 2018 to present, and developed a framework for quality assessment. This systematic literature review will help us test both the applicability of the surveillance knowledge inventory as well as the ease of adding data to the inventories.
- We also planned to perform an analysis of the data on *T. gondii*-seroprevalence in participants of the “Status of Health in Pomerania” (SHiP) study in comparison with the national cohort (Wilking et al, 2014). A literature analysis on seroprevalence and source attribution of *T. gondii* in humans was to accompany this analysis. Both studies are related to partners outside the EJP consortium. Due to changes in personnel that cannot be influenced by the FLI, it is not clear if these analyses can be finished within EJP Orion.
- Although One Health Pilot 1 is delayed because of missing personnel, resources (the recruitment process was delayed by COVID 19) we expect to complete the systematic literature review by the end of EJP Orion.
- A systematic review on surveillance systems on *T. gondii* in feed and food will be carried out. With this pilot study, we will be able to test the Rasch model and assess its practical applicability. We will focus on *T. gondii* in feed and food and thereby complement the similar analysis in animal health performed by the FLI. To make the analysis more comprehensive, we will network with the EJP project TOXOSOURCE in early 2021. This project deals with the source attribution of *T. gondii* infections. We will analyse the usability of the Rasch model for future surveillance systems under development. Due to staff changes, the pilot project is behind schedule. However, it will be completed by the end of the project period.

JIP1-WP2-T3-ST2: One Health Pilot 2: Salmonella (carried out by APHA & PHE, UK) (M7-M39) (M7-M39)

- The plan for the pilot study has been developed and agreed. A document detailing experiences regarding whole genome sequence data sharing processes and lessons learnt from experiences during 2019 is in development, which will be used to develop recommendations for the final project outputs. A data sharing protocol and draft Memorandum of Understanding is in development.

JIP1-WP2-T3-ST3 One Health Pilot 3: Hepatitis E (carried out by WBVR and RIVM, the Netherlands) (M7-M39)

- Data about hepatitis E surveillance done in different institutes belonging to different sectors are gathered and put in a country map. The country map consists of surveillance components or monitoring projects per sector and institute and data sharing among these sectors for a disease or pathogen. To make the country map broadly useable for others, an instruction of how to complete the map was made and will be tested. Following the results on our country map, the goal is to set up and enhance inter-sectoral (all identified institutes in the country map) collaboration for hepatitis E. This has come to a standstill, due to the corona-crisis.

JIP1-WP2-T3-ST4 One Health Pilot 3: AMR (carried out by Sciensano, Belgium) (M7-M39)

- The plan for the pilot study was developed. The plan includes the objectives, the expected outcome as well as information on collaboration and reporting of the results. The aim of this pilot project is to enlighten the network of collaboration between the authorities and the scientists in term of surveillance of antibioresistance in Belgium, in analysing the participation of scientists in national meetings where topics related to OH AMR surveillance or monitoring are discussed (focus: operations and communication).
- Advance of the project: the scientists involved in the pilot were informed begin of March 2020, and ready to collaborate, but the CoV-SARS-2 outbreak put the whole project on hold, as all AMR-related-meetings were cancelled. Moreover, the Competent Authority (due to the Cov-SARS-2 situation) has delayed the implementation of a National Action Plan on AMR. The pilot project was then re-started in September 2020 and performed until the end of Y3.

JIP1-WP2-T3-ST5 One Health Pilot 5: Application of Rasch model on data collected in questionnaires (carried out by BfR and FLI, Germany) (M7-M39)

- The quality of a surveillance program cannot be directly observed or measured. However, it is a fundamental characteristic of a surveillance program. An attempt is made to estimate the quality of surveillance programs by means of a questionnaire. A list of characteristics of the different programs is compiled. Based on the questionnaires describing the properties of surveillance projects a set of quality scores are planned to be calculated by the use of a Rasch model. By this application of a method developed and validated in JIP1-WP2-T2-ST2 - Data analysis and validation on data collected in JIP1-WP2-T2-ST1 - Data collection and integration we optimize the information gain and further examine the practical applicability of the method collection. With the results, we provide a base for a ranking of surveillance systems and for the discussion of the properties of recent surveillance projects under the framework of one-health. Project status: Model is coded and validated. Results will be

calculated immediately after feedback of questionnaires. Because the response rate of the questionnaires cannot be estimated, the Rasch model is additionally applied to the surveillance systems for *T. gondii* conducted in Germany to test the performance of the model.

Task T-2Epi.4: Evaluation and Recommendations Epi (M31-M42)

Survey and/or interviews with internal / external experts:

- The final inventories were developed based on the feedback of internal and external experts

OH knowledge base-epi:

- The established knowledge base is a living document that is continuously updated by the WP members.

WP2 - NGS

JIP1-WP2-T5: Improving OH Knowledge Base – NGS (M13-M24)

- With regards to the NGS handbook, the focus for the reporting period has been on building the framework for the book, and on content creation. For this purpose, we have run several writing workshops during the spring of 2020. The technical platform that is being used for the handbook is Github, with display of the handbook via Readthedocs. We have deposited a preliminary version of the handbook as a deliverable on M36. The contents that will go into the handbook were more closely described in the M21 report. Our pathogen of choice for the pilot has been *L. monocytogenes*, and due to that, we have had a particular focus on methods for typing and characterizing that pathogen for the handbook. We are collaborating with the BeONE EJP project for continuance of the handbook.

JIP1-WP2-T6: NGS OH pilot studies (M7-M39)

- For the OSLO pilot project, the focus has been on getting the technical analysis platform up and running in Y3. We have chosen to use IRIDA as our platform (<https://www.irida.ca/>). This platform is currently up and running. We are using the Norwegian Research and Education Cloud (<https://www.nrec.no/>) as our infrastructure provider, and are in the process of establishing a contract with them in collaboration with other projects at the NVI and the NIPH. Within this platform, we currently have a working pipeline for *L. monocytogenes*. This pipeline will be published during Q1 2021 to enable use by others using the Galaxy/IRIDA platform. We had planned to perform a national table top exercise focusing on an outbreak scenario in Q2 of 2020; this has been postponed to spring 2021, provided the Covid situation improves.

JIP1-WP2-T7: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

- We are continuing to get feedback from the work done in related pilot studies to improve the OH Knowledgebase - NGS. Due to the interaction with the pilots, and the delays caused by Covid, this optimization process will continue to the end of the project.

WP2 - Integration

JIP1-WP2-T8: Improving OH Knowledge Base – Integration (M13-M24)

- The WP hosted a workshop in January 2020 to integrate the work done in the country

specific pilots into the overarching work of ORION, by discussing what tools were developed and trialled in the pilots and how they fitted within the OHS Codex framework. The workshop was held in Copenhagen and co-hosted by SVA and DTU.

- Each pilot was presented by a flash-presentation after which everyone else had the opportunity to provide input, suggestions and identify synergies with other work. A generic template for evaluating impact and outcomes of each pilot study was also discussed and as was the capture and reporting of lessons learned. Furthermore, the OHS Codex was discussed from the perspective of how the pilot studies feed into the pillars. A strategy for how lessons learned would be captured and communicated as part of the Codex framework was implemented.
- Co-developed an ORION template for reporting outcomes and lesson learned from pilot projects

JIP1-WP2-T9: Integration OH pilot studies (M7-M39)

- The three pilot projects in WP2 integration have been progressing, albeit slowly in 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has not affected the studies directly, but have caused a drain on both epidemiology and laboratory expertise in public health. Even though we have attempted to make up for this on the food and veterinary side, the pilots do need public health inputs, as the collaboration is the nature of the projects.

Pilot: Enhancing the One Health-ness of interpretation of AMR and AMU surveillance data for zoonoses

- In 2019, this pilot generated a One Health focussed way of reporting AMR in *Campylobacter* by integrating data integrating the five relevant data streams of AMU for treatment in humans and animals and AMR in animals and food and people. DANMAP link
- In 2020, the work focussed on a similar objective for *Salmonella* and the project group met early in the year to plan the flow in the chapter and the sections. The objective was to emphasise the One Health focus, whilst still ensuring that information in other serotypes relevant for national control plans was maintained. The work on the chapters is currently ongoing, data is in the process of integration, and mutual data interpretation is taking place. Even though the ambition for the *Salmonella* chapter was slightly reduced due to COVID-19, the chapter for DANMAP 2019 contained an improved One Health *Salmonella* chapter. Both the enhanced OH sections were published in DANMAP 2019 and after that the templates will be written up as resources for the OHS Codex. These results were used as examples of integrated OH surveillance in presentations for various audiences e.g. Danish Veterinary and Food administration, PAHO WHO, 2020 International Symposium on One Health AMR in the Republic of Korea

*Pilot: Explore the additional value of integration of multiple *Campylobacter* surveillance data streams from animal health and food safety*

- This objective is integrating surveillance data and register-data from 2-3 surveillance components across animal health and food safety for *Campylobacter* in Denmark. The aim is to enhance the surveillance value by looking at the whole farm-to-fork-to-human exposure chain by carrying out integrated analyses and cross-sector interpretation. Data from 2013-2018 was received from industry and government, which were combined with surveillance data sets available at DTU. The data was cleaned and harmonized using R

programme files and outliers and missing values were identified and discussed with data owners. The data and metadata was described and the analyst acquired an in-depth understanding of the surveillance components and the data. Towards the end of the 2019, the data was further collated with the national CHR database to allow for geo-referencing and identification of production type of the flocks at the time of sampling.

- Integration between the surveillance data and the national register data at flock-level over time was not beneficial. Due to data quality, too many missing values were created and the attempt was abandoned and instead the data was integrated at farm/premise level. Encouragement for better and more precise registration in the surveillance programme was fed back to data providers. Better data quality will increase the sustainability of the data by expanding its uses. Analyses plans were drawn and the data is in process of being analysed across data-streams and sectors to add value to the traditional sector specific surveillance.
- One of the main outputs is near completion and the integration of the surveillance data streams has enabled development of a risk-based *Campylobacter* control programme, including predicting its effect on risk of *Campylobacteriosis* in humans. It targets the farms that poses highest risk to public health. The programme was discussed with the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration and the largest poultry producing companies in DK. Currently, the risk managers are considering whether and how to include the developed programme in the National *Campylobacter* Action Plan and we will continue to work with them to make it applicable and applied. A scientific publication is also in preparation.

Pilot: A coherent description of a surveillance system from farm-to-patient

- The work continues to be developed and modified to encompass animal, food and human surveillance data. Processes along the surveillance chain were described including target populations, sampling methods, laboratory methods, data analyses, actors and stakeholders. Descriptive results of the different components will be presented alongside the detailed data and metadata descriptions. This work is currently inactive and it is uncertain whether it will be completed beyond the current discussions and information sharing due to staff changes in our collaborative public health institute. Results achieved so far are prepared for publication.

WP3 - OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure

JIP1-WP3-T3: One health pilot (M7-M39)

- Every year since 2009 a national report on the outcome of surveillance activities of infectious diseases in animals and humans is produced in Sweden. The report is produced with contributions from the animal health-, public health- and food safety sector. The Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) coordinates the production of the report. The purpose of the pilot was to strengthen the OH-focus of the report and to create and implement a work-process supporting the collaboration between sectors that will persist after the project ends. Moreover, the agencies will through the process gain a better understanding of each other's activities, data sources and results.

JIP1-WP3-T4: Evaluation and Recommendations (M31-M42)

- From months 31 to 36, we have reviewed the results of the pilot nationally, in order to

provide recommendations for the next cycle of surveillance reporting. This activity has resulted in the establishment of strengthened collaboration between animal health, public health and food safety surveillance in Sweden.

- The plan for months 36 to 42 is now to focus on the generalization of the lessons, from the Swedish pilot in particular, and for the activities of WP3 in general, into outputs that can be adopted by other countries. We aim to produce a deliverable discoursing on the different opportunities for surveillance data production and consumption in member states and in the chain of reporting to EFSA/ECDC, all the way to the publishing of reports by these agencies. For each of these data production or consumption points, we will point out the lessons learned on how data providers could improve data interoperability, the costs associated with doing so, and the potential benefits for surveillance and health. All proof-of-concept examples and tools developed within ORION will be presented within this data workflow continuum. The results are largely focused, but not restricted to Swedish pilot.

WP4 - Coordination, Communication, Training and Sustainability

JIP1-WP4-T1: Internal project coordination (M1-M42)

- The project coordination continued to use the shared project management resources on Google, the ORION Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and promoted the adoption of the EJP Website and EJP ORION groups (an internal and a public group).
- The coordination holds trimonthly web meetings for the whole ORION consortium (including EFSA, ECDC, EJP WPs and interested other EJP project leads) and a monthly call for the WP leaders & deputy leaders.
- For all web-meetings the ORION coordination created meeting minutes that were shared via email and the ORION VRE.

JIP1-WP4-T2: External project integration (synchronized with EJP WP5) (M1-M42)

- The project coordination contributed to relevant overarching EJP activities and continued to extend collaboration and information exchange specifically with the new EJP projects.
- EFSA / ECDC were actively informed on project results via the “EJP ORION WP1 & WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA & ECDC”
- ORION successfully applied to host the 2020 CPD Module. This event will take place in February 2021.
- ORION kept close collaboration with the JIP COHESIVE and JIP MATRIX, and exchanged experiences through dedicated meetings. ORION also kept close collaboration with the JRP NOVA, focused on surveillance.
- To ensure complementarity and avoid duplication of work with new EJP projects, ORION presented results in a cogwheel workshop on October 6th, 2020 (please see trainings below)

JIP1-WP4-T3: Sustainability roadmap (M7-M42)

- For the majority of ORION solutions first activities were undertaken in 2020 to guarantee the short-to-medium term sustainability. This included a number of dissemination and publication activities as well as the adoption of technical infrastructure that supports long-

term maintenance and collaboration. A first revised version of the Sustainability roadmap was created by the end of 2020.

JIP1-WP4-T4: Training and Dissemination (M1-M42)

JIP1-WP4-T4-ST2: Knowledge integration (web portal, Wiki, curricula, tutorials, videos, sample data) (M7-M42)

- Continuous updates performed on ORION's main online platform "OHS Codex" as well as on individual web resources that each partner created for their specific solution, e.g. for OHEJP Glossary linked resources the website <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/> was created and updated regularly

JIP1-WP4-T4-ST3: Training and support for other EJP projects & partners (M7-M42)

- ORION co-organized the NGS online workshop in April 2020
- Participation in ASM2020 with 2 presentations & 2-3 posters
- ORION presented own results during a dedicated EJP Cogwheel workshop on October 6th, 2020 to EJP members. The recording will be made available by OHEJP-WP4.
- ORION presented the status from the WP1-WP3 supra-national pilot with EFSA-ECDC during EFSA's 38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses Monitoring Data on 19-20 October 2020
- ORION results were accepted as posters / oral presentation during several international conferences: ICBO 2020 Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW) (16th September 2020), WOHC 2020 (30th Oct - 03rd Nov. 2020) and the 4th ICAHS 2020 (11th -13th November 2020)
- Selected ORION project results will support training during the 2020 EJP CPD module (workshop planned from 15th - 19th February 2021)
- A number of extended webinars on specific tools (e.g. EJP Glossary text processing tool, the LOD tool, OH-CRAC etc.) are planned to take place on the spring of 2021.

3.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

3.3.1. Deliverables

- NO deliverables due in Year 3 (2020), as by the approved project extension all deliverables were moved into Y4
- The following deliverables are due in Year 4 (2021)

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
ORION	D-1.3	Revised OH Surveillance Codex, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42		M42			4, 5
ORION	D-2.7	Revised OH Knowledge Base - Epi, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42		M42			5
ORION	D-2.8	Revised OH Knowledge Base -NGS, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42		M42			1,2,3,4
ORION	D-2.9	Revised OH Knowledge Base - Integration, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42		M42			1, 2,4,5,6
ORION	D-3.3	Revised OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub, including lessons learned from the OH pilots	M42		M42	partly		3, 4, 5
ORION	D-4.4	Revised Sustainability Roadmap	M42		M42			8
ORION	D-4.5	OHS Knowledge Hub populated with resources from WP1, WP2 and WP3	M42		M42			4,5
ORION	D-4.6	Two additional training workshops and two webinars	M42		M42			8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

3.3.2. Milestones

- NO milestone due in Year 3 (2020), as by the approved project extension all milestones were moved into Y4
- The following milestone is due in Year 4 (2021)

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
ORION	M-IA1.ORION.3	ORION evaluation workshop	M39			

3.4. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged ?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Data interoperability in health surveillance: a literature review to support the development of One Health frameworks (SUBMITTED)	yes		Not yet approved for publication, but planned as gold access in the Journal of Biomedical Semantics - JBSM-D-20-00030
Toxoplasma gondii infection and toxoplasmosis in farm animals: Risk factors and economic impact (PUBLISHED), DOI: http://doi.org/10.1016/j.fawpar.2019.e00037	yes		yes (1580 €)
One Health Surveillance Codex: promoting the adoption of One Health solutions within and across European countries (Accepted)	yes		Accepted for publication with minor revisions as a gold open access paper in the journal "One Health"
Houe, H., Nielsen, SS., Nielsen, LR., Ethelberg, S., Mølbak, K. (2020). Opportunities for Improved Disease Surveillance and Control by Use of Integrated Data on Animal and Human Health. <i>Frontiers in Veterinary Medicine</i> , 6: 301, pp. 1-8. DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00301	yes		yes
Joensen, KG., Kiil, K., Gantzhorn, MR., Nauerby, B., Engberg, J., Holt, HM., Nielsen, HL., Petersen, AM., Kuhn, KG., Sandø, G., Ethelberg, S., Nielsen, EM. (2020). Whole-Genome Sequencing to Detect Numerous <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> Outbreaks and Match Patient Isolates to Sources, Denmark, 2015–2017. <i>Emerging Infectious Diseases</i> , 26(3), 523-532. DOI: https://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid2603.190947	yes		yes

Additional output

- Presentation in the Integrated Food Ontology Workshop (IFOW), part of the the 11th International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies (ICBO 2020). Proceedings paper freely available in this link . Title: Health Surveillance Ontology: supporting semantic interoperability in One-Health.
- Korsgaard, H. B., Ellis-Iversen, J., Hendriksen, R. S., Borck Høg, B., Ronco, T., Attauabi, M., Boel, J., Dalby, T., Hammerum, A. M., Hansen, F., Hasman, H., Henius, A. E., Hoffmann, S., Ilan, M. B., Kaya, H., Kjerulf, A., Kristensen, B., Kähler, J., Rhod Larsen, A., ... Laursen, M. (2020). DANMAP 2019 - Use of antimicrobial agents and occurrence of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria from food animals, food and humans in Denmark. Statens Serum Institut og Technical University of Denmark. WWW.DANMAP.ORG
- All available Swedish reports on “Surveillance of infectious diseases in animals and humans” (2006 to 2020) were published with unique identifiers in the Swedish data portal for open public information.
- One dataset compiling all surveillance data available in the reports, including surveillance methods annotated according to the OH-CRAC principles² developed in ORION (consensus report annotation checklist), was also published in the Swedish data portal in both human readable format (comma separated values, CSV) and machine readable format (RDF). The latter is explicitly annotated with machine readable surveillance concepts from the Health Surveillance Ontology. All permanent unique identifiers created are listed at: <http://datadrivensurveillance.org/campylobacter-surveillance-in-sweden>
- M. Filter, T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, E. Lopez de Abechuco, E. M. Sundermann, J. Ellis-Iversen, J. Gethmann, K. Lagesen, V. De Waele, G. Boseret, F. Dórea. The OH Surveillance (OHS) Codex - a high level framework supporting mutual understanding and information exchange between One Health sectors. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May; Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20372/users/1051/download>
- E. Lopez de Abechuco (BfR): Introduction to ORION project. Cogwheel workshop, 28th April 2020. Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20376/users/1051/download>
- E. Lopez de Abechuco, F. Dorea, T. Buschhardt, T. Günther, E. Sundermann, N. Scaccia, A. Foddai, M. Dispas, M. Umaer, M. Holmberg, J. Gethmann, M. Filter. One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a generic checklist to support harmonization of surveillance data reports. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May (Oral presentation). Link to presentation: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20371/users/1051/download>
- N. Scaccia, T. Guenther, T. Buschhardt, L. Valentin, M. Filter. Text mining technology as added-value infrastructure to the One Health EJP Glossary. OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th May (Poster). Link to poster: <https://onehealth.ejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/128/files/20373/users/1051/download>
- Gethmann, J. et al Poster Presentations during the ASM Scientific conference 2020: The ORION project – OH knowledge base “surveillance systems” OHEJP ASM 2020, 27th-29th

² <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/5-the-dissemination-principle.html>

May (Poster).

- A set of prototypic OH-LOD web services were established that facilitates the semi-automatic mapping of concepts from the EFSA's SSD catalogues into the new HSO. Another web service allows to convert Excel-based surveillance data into the data exchange format RDF by exploiting HSO. The generated RDF surveillance data files are now accessible for semantic search technologies and services that make use of linked open data.
- A prototypic "Glossaryfication web service" was created that automatically identifies matching glossary terms in a user-defined document and in this way helps users to create document specific glossaries annexes. This will help to avoid misinterpretation of terms defined differently in certain OH sectors in the future and add value to the OHEJP Glossary.

3.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

WP1:

- collaborated with MATRIX, NOVA, COHESIVE project on joint improving the WP1 tools like the OHEJP Glossary, the OH CRAC or the OHS Codex
- ORION and MATRIX established a collaboration plan in order to continue extending the OHS Codex once the ORION project finalizes
- during the Cogwheel workshop held in November 2020, participants of the SafeConsume project showed interest in the OHS Codex and the possibilities of adding new resources. A meeting between ORION, MATRIX and SafeConsume has been organized for January 2021 to continue with the discussion
- Extensive collaboration with EFSA & ECDC in a dedicated WP1-WP3 supra-national pilot with 10+ web meetings and an on premise visit at EFSA in February 2020
-

WP2-Epi:

- collaborated with representatives of EFSA and ECDC on the details and sustainability questions of the inventories
- collaboration with COHESIVE and RaDAR project
- collaboration with EJP MATRIX to support MATRIX in using the data and methods from WP2-Epi

WP2-Integration

- pilot projects are intertwined with the Danish Integrated Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring and Research Programme (DANMAP)
- the pilot project on data integration is working with the Danish Action Plan on Campylobacter in Food and Environment and is developing solutions and collaboration with the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration and the poultry industries in Denmark.

WP2-NGS:

- collaboration with LISTADAPT (building bioinformatics pipelines for Listeria)

- collaboration with EFSA regarding tool set for pipelines for WGS analysis of L. monocytogenes
- collaboration with the COHESIVE project regarding databases for sequence data
- collaboration with the EJP BeOne project regarding continuance of the NGS handbook project
- collaboration with the NVI project SEQ-TECH regarding continuance of the ORION established IRIDA analysis platform.
- collaboration with the IRIDA project regarding establishment of the IRIDA platform in Oslo

WP3:

- collaboration with the BeONE project concerning data harmonisation and interoperability
- hosted regular meetings with the IRIDA consortium in Canada, and their team developing the GenEpiO ontology
- collaboration with national projects within SWEDEN → ontology development was partly funded by the Swedish Agency for Innovation (Vinnova). Data interoperability issues were developed in collaboration with projects on data-driven surveillance financed by the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)
- kept close contact with the EFSA initiative SIGMA, in order to ensure complementarity of results and avoid duplication of work in what regards data interoperability in OH surveillance, and reporting of surveillance data from member states to EFSA.

WP4:

- continued to maintain the contact with the Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (Switzerland)
- attended regular meeting with the SISOT team from WHO/FAO/OIE (in collaboration with the MATRIX project)
- attended and presented ORION at EJP cogwheel workshops
- presented ORION at the Stakeholders Committee meeting of the One Health EJP (12th October 2020)

3.6. Data Management Plan

- The ORION DMP has been uploaded to the EJP portal group ORION. It can be downloaded after login to the EJP portal by ORION project members via: https://onehealthejp.eu/?get_group_doc=34/1609877262-JAN2020DMPQuestionnaire_v2_ORION_WP3WP2intWP2NGSWP2epi_WP4_MF.xlsx
- The ORION DMP comprises a description of all the data generated in the project.
- FAIR principles will be fulfilled for all those ORION results where these principles are applicable. Certain ORION results, e.g. some prototypic web services and software tools, might not be fully compliant to FAIR principles as this cannot be accomplished for prototypic software tools with reasonable effort. Nevertheless, it is possible to access the source code of these software tools and in this way build on ORION results.

3.7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of Ethical Reviewers, January 2018	Project's measures and actions taken at the end of 2018	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2019	Comments Project Leaders, end of 2019	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments Project Leaders, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020	Comments Project Leaders, January 2021
The applicants must confirm the compliance with <u>GDPR</u>	In WP1, no data from individuals will be collected or used. We see no risk of infringing the GDPR. In WP2Epi, no data from individuals will be collected or used. We see no risk of infringing the GDPR. In WP2-NGS, we might utilize some human related pseudonymized metadata for sequences that we might seek to analyze in collaboration with other EJP projects,	As regard to the proposed interviews with volunteering key personnel (WP2int 2.3), an informed consent procedure should have been established and proposed to the research participants. It must mention the rights to participants as described in GDPR,	Informed consent was established with reference to GDPR by the Data Protection Officer and according to the existing rules. In the end, contact persons emails were omitted from the report, only publishing the organisational contact point emails already available on the web.	As a reminder of one important part of GRPD, the beneficiaries must provide the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained.	BfR: dsb@bfr.bund.de SVA: jerker.plobeck@sva.se DTU: Joell@food.dtu.dk for data from ORION The overarching DPO of DTU is: anesa@dtu.dk FLI: Martina.Rychly@fli.de NVI: Siv.Gunhild.Boe-Tondevold@vetinst.no Sciensano: dpo@sciensano.be NIPH: Erlend.Bakken@fhi.no FOHM: dataskyddsbud@folkhalsomyndigheten.se	Could you confirm that the other partners, e.g. niph, ssi, fohm, coda-cerva, wbvr, rivm, apha, phe, are not collecting any personal data?	Sciensano: No personal, private or confidential information were collected. SSI: We store all Danish human metadata used in the project on servers approved for use for human sensitive data in-house at SSI.

	<p>however, these will if so be stored on an e-infrastructure approved for use for human sensitive data set up in Norway.</p> <p>For WP2int 2.3 - Requirement analysis for an “OH Knowledge Base – Integration”, professional email addresses of individuals were volunteered in the screening questionnaires. Interviews with volunteering key personnel of some initiatives was recorded and the original sound files will be kept in a restricted folder complying with ORION data management</p>	<p>among which the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained through the interviews.</p> <p>It is not clear that the above documents were used for the questionnaire work</p>			<p>SSI: compliance@ssi.dk</p>	<p>RIVM, WBVR, APHA, PHE: confirmed that they are not collecting personal data for the ORION project</p> <p>All other ORION partners: now provided the contact details of the responsible data protection officer</p>
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	<p>plans, DTU data management plans, DTUs Policy of the Retention of Primary Materials and Data, GDPR, until deletion on the last day of the ORION project. In WP3, no data from individual cases or laboratory tests will be used, only data already aggregated at the surveillance level, and already made public by the owner institution. We see no risk of infringing the GDPR</p>						
<p>The applicants must specify whether</p>	<p>The human genome will not be sequenced in any</p>	<p>Satisfactory reply to the genome</p>		<p>Nothing Pending - Closed</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

<p><u>human genome</u> will also be sequenced in the pilot study. In case of whole genome analysis a procedure to address any incidental / adverse findings must be prepared and available.</p>	<p>of ORION's pilot studies</p>	<p>analysis issue</p>					
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3.8. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information:

WP2-NGS has not strictly speaking lost personnel as such, but as the majority of the participating institutions are public health institutions, the manpower that has been available for project work has been significantly reduced. Fortunately, some of this slack has been able to be taken in by other institutions, however, the outputs of this WP is likely to be a bit downscaled from what was previously projected.

3.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	ICBO 2020 Integrated Food Ontology Workshop – oral (online) presentation		
Date:	September 30 th , 2020		
Place:	Online due to COVID		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	10		

Name of the activity:	Parma summer school – presentation: Surveillance systems and data interoperability under the One Health goal		
Date:	June 10 th , 2020		
Place:	Online due to COVID		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	100	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	20		

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2020 – poster presentation: The ORION project – OH Knowledge base “surveillance systems”		
Date:	May 27-29 th , 2020		
Place:	Online due to COVID https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Cogwheel workshop with InfAct: "Introduction to ORION project"		
Date:	22 nd January 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Cogwheel workshop with JPIAMR: "Introduction to ORION project"		
Date:	28 th April 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Oral Presentations during the ASM Scientific conference: "The OH Surveillance (OHS) Codex - a high level framework supporting mutual understanding and information exchange between One Health sectors"		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Oral Presentations during the ASM Scientific conference: "One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a generic checklist to support harmonization of surveillance data reports"		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster Presentations during the ASM Scientific conference: "Text mining technology as added-value infrastructure to the One Health EJP Glossary"		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Cogwheel workshop: "ORION project" – with contributions from all ORION WPs		
Date:	5 th October 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	38th meeting of the Scientific Network for Zoonoses Monitoring Data: "ORION EFSA-ECDC joint pilot"		
Date:	19-20 October 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster Presentations during the World One Health Congress : “One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist (OH-CRAC): a framework for harmonization of surveillance data reports”		
Date:	30 th October-3 rd November 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	
Industry	50	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster Presentations during the World One Health Congress : “The "Glossaryfication" web service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community”		
Date:	30 th October-3 rd November 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	
Industry	50	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Cogwheel workshop with SafeConsume: "Introduction to ORION project"		
Date:	25 th November 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting (webinar on the practical use of NGS)
Date:	April 29 th , 2020
Place:	Online due to COVID
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories	

	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

4. JIP2 - COHESIVE

4.1. Summary of the work carried out

As stated earlier, the coming together and extensively discuss issues in a physical meeting is very important for an integrative project such as COHESIVE. In addition to work on the content of the project, the getting to know each other and build trust and respect is key as well. Unfortunately, this was hampered strongly due to the COVID-19 epidemic. However, after in first instance delaying in the hope for physical meetings, resilience was shown and the communication of all tasks was switched towards virtual meetings and workshops. Also, the reduced capacity within especially public health institutes led to delay of several tasks.

For Task 2.1 the main goal is to develop guidelines for *national* One Health systems or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary-food collaborations, with the aim to improve signalling, risk assessment and response (risk analysis) to zoonoses. A lot of information has been gathered throughout the project and is currently turned into a guideline. The guideline will be web-based and eventually linked to the MedVetNet association website to be able to maintain the guideline also after OHEJP ends. Within Task 2.3 several pilots are planned, in which Belgium, Portugal, Norway and Italy will go through the first steps of the guidelines. In three countries a core group (change agents) has been established and a stakeholder analysis is (partly) performed. However, due to COVID-19 the systems mapping workshops have all been delayed.

For Task 2.2 the goal is to develop an online decision support tool to help the user decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The tool will direct the user to one of fourteen resources, which include guidance documents, tools and models. The tool is completed as version 1 and it is live, a web address has been circulated to EJP members. The deliverable JIP2-2.3 associated with this task was delivered in Dec 2019, however it has been significantly improved since and work is ongoing to move a copy of it to the EJP website. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge and tool improvements are continued to be made as they are identified through feedback in the project.

Task 3.1: The task focuses on identifying factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals of zoonotic events within and between countries. Interviews with persons working within food safety, public health and veterinary medicine at central, regional or local level were performed in six countries. The thematic analysis of the interview data has been finalized at the national level and a joint thematic analysis is ongoing.

For Task 3.2 a follow-up of the horizon scanning pilot exercise regarding One Health that took place in Nov 2019 has been conducted. The main drivers for One Health were considered to be political and decision making behaviour, people and consumer behaviour, science and innovations, market behaviour, new and re-emerging pathogens or threats and climate change.

For Task 3.3 the aim is to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. Hantavirus and Q-fever in the UK were chosen to be retrospectively analyzed. All UK-government publications relating to Hantavirus and Q-fever have been compiled and their data-sources tracked and mapped. A general European-level Q-fever surveillance map has been made in a similar way, using input from consortium members and available online publications. Following an initial systems mapping, with a specific focus on Q-Fever, a number of potential improvements for surveillance in England have been identified and will be highlighted to animal health surveillance colleagues in the beginning of 2021.

For Task 3.4, pilot One-Health Early Warning System, the aim is to build on the findings of the previous tasks (i.e. tasks 2.1, 3.1, 3.2) and share low threshold potential signals for pathogens with One Health impacts across multiple countries within the consortium. Through the initial meeting we can build relationships between countries and start a forum that can continue post-project and is seen as being of value for the long term. Unfortunately, due to the outbreak of highly pathogenic avian influenza across Northern Europe the first meeting has been further postponed until the early 2021.

For Task 3.5, development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (CBA), the aim is to build on previous experience of CBA to produce a tool and/or method that is applicable to zoonotic pathogens. As CBA can vary due to within country specific conditions that affect both costs and benefits, having a common method attempts to make the CBA comparable across countries. A literature review of CBA methods is underway, with the aim of producing a report focusing on the similarities, differences, strengths and weaknesses of different models and methods. This will incorporate input from other OHEJP members to gather CBA experience from across the OHEJP consortium. The systematic review will culminate in a framework for optimizing CBA studies which would help to ensure that future studies are harmonized and directly comparable.

For WP4.1 the aim is to develop a prototype information system at the national level allowing different databases to be interoperable. A survey has been conducted to gather detailed information on existing databases and information systems for WGS data management and analysis adopted or available among countries. A demo version of the COHESIVE prototype information system (CIS) is made and available for Italy. The feasibility studies in The Netherlands, Italy and Norway are ongoing. Italy feasibility study is almost finished, while the others have some delay.

In WP4.2, the development of the tracing web portal - FoodChain-Lab Web – (FCL Web) advanced further. A revised login procedure and data security documents were developed and FCL Web is available in production mode. Also, a JSON-based data exchange format allows for analyzing delivery data from a data collection mask developed in a national project in FCL Web.

In WP4.3. the development of shiny app for quantitative risk assessment is completed in the first step. A user-friendly menu structure was implemented for the development of complex quantitative models. For saving and loading models, the JSON exchange format and the RDA format were developed. The user has the possibility to perform a data fitting with an own data set and simulate models by 1- or 2- dim. Monte-Carlo simulation. After the simulation, the user can directly view the results in the app. Afterwards, the user has the possibility to download a comprehensive report as pdf, which includes all results. Model uncertainties, parameter uncertainties and scenario uncertainties can be documented based on the BfR Guidance Document for Uncertainty Analysis in Exposure Assessment.

4.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Coordination, communication and sustainability

JIP2-WP1-T1: Coordination (M1-M36)

The steering group is meeting online every 5 weeks. In these meetings all tasks are discussed shortly, including (possible) problems. Also general tasks are discussed and decided upon, such as annual meetings and reports. There have been several contacts with EFSA, mainly concerning WP4, but also regular video-conferences are organized between the contact persons of EFSA and the coordinator of COHESIVE. Unfortunately, ECDC didn't have a contact person available for COHESIVE, but a new person will be appointed. ORION and NOVA are other OHEJP projects to which COHESIVE closely relates. ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE are working together at a glossary including terms used within the different projects. A publication is in preparation. The new partners VRI and ANSES started in the different tasks mainly by participation in workshops and the annual meeting in 2019. This continued

in 2020, although further integration was hampered especially for ANSES and VRI due to COVID-19. INIAV, who became a partner earlier than VRI and ANSES, did manage to integrate fully and is very much involved in WP2 and WP3.

JIP2-WP1-T2: Communication/dissemination (M1-M36)

Since in 2019 two general (annual) meetings were organized, the annual meeting that was planned in March 2020, was postponed. Due to many planned conferences (i.e. World One Health Conference, ASM OHEJP, IAFP European Symposium on Food Safety Food) in Spring it was postponed to Autumn. Due to COVID-19 we transformed the annual meeting into a virtual one, which took place on November 24th and 26th. The annual meeting was open to all OHEJP members and stakeholders. Indeed members from other projects were present as well as EFSA, ECDC and FAO. EFSA also gave a presentation. As a spin-off, we had organized a workshop on systems thinking as a satellite workshop before the ASM in Prague. However, this could not go through. Also the workshop during the IAFP European Symposium on Food Safety conference was cancelled. The outbreak preparedness workshop for PhD students, which was cancelled only a few days in advance due to the large COVID-19 outbreak, eventually took place as a virtual event. This is a very important topic which fits very well within the key issues COHESIVE wants to address (be prepared in a One Health fashion for emerging zoonoses) and which is more than ever relevant. There are also regular meetings with project leaders from all integrative projects, led by the OHEJP WP4 leader. Other dissemination activities that did take place, related to the other work packages, are indicated below.

WP2. Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

JIP2-WP2-T1: Development of guidelines for national One Health structures (M1-M26)

The main goal of this task is the development of guidelines in order to support countries to set up/strengthen the collaboration between the human-vet-food domains with respect to signaling, risk assessment, response and control of zoonoses. During the general meeting in Rome in November 2019 it was decided to disseminate the guidelines as a website. This would facilitate easy searching of dedicated information, based on the needs of the user. An outline of the website has been made. The webdesigner currently is transferring our wishes into a layout. Already a lot of information has been gathered during the workshops in 2018 and 2019 This information is in the process of being transferred into useful information for the users of the website. In the workshops also information has been gathered on barriers that can be faced when trying to organize risk analysis of zoonoses in a One Health fashion. Important barriers such as obtaining political will and building trust are deepened by performing dedicated interviews. The interviews are analysed and the results will be translated into tips and tricks in the guidelines to support countries with these kind of barriers. After the OHEJP ends, the guideline-website will be transferred to the MedVetNet Association (MVNA) and linked to their website, to secure long term sustainability.

There is regular contact with the FAO with respect to the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) of OIE, WHO and FAO, specifically in relation to the SISOT work group, and now also contacts are made with the WHO in relation to the governance part of the TZG.

It became clear in the first 2 years, that physical workshops are the best way to co-create the guidelines. Because the results from a workshop are input for the next and good preparation is key to a successful meeting, the workshops can't be too close together. Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 no physical workshop has taken place this year. After postponing workshops a couple of times, at a certain moment we had to conclude that physical meetings were no longer an option in 2020. Therefore, we started organizing virtual workshops. Learning by doing, it turned out that also now good preparation

was essential. The preparation is very labor-intensive and even though the participants are engaged, the output is limited compared to physical meetings. Partly, because the assignments are more complicated to perform online and partly because people are only dedicated for a short period of time (2 hours) instead of i.e. 2 days. This did result in quite a delay of this task. Another additional factor for the delay is the fact that key personell, especially in public health organisations were occupied in COVID-19 activities and therefore not available for COHESIVE activities. The timeline until June 2021 is very tight for this task. Although we will be able to deliver a website with guidelines by that time, the quality most likely will be affected by the COVID-19 crisis.

Figure 1: Draft picture illustrating the stepping stones for the implementation process which will be included in the website ‘One Health: Setting up a risk analysis system for zoonoses.’

JIP2-WP2-T2: Development of structured decision making (M1-M24)

The deliverable for this task was delivered during 2019, this produced a prototype tool of a decision tree framework to help the user decide on the most appropriate method to use when tasked with conducting a risk assessment for a specific situation. The tool has been significantly improved since the delivery in 2019. The tool is designed so that it can be updated as new risk assessment resources emerge. The tool will direct the user to one of fourteen resources, which include guidance documents, tools and models. The tool, now run in a javascript-enabled browser, has supporting text outlining purpose and caveats, and has adopted EJP colours. It references the grant agreement in a footer, and also provides links to the OHEJP homepage and EJP homepage. No further dissemination activities have been done, however a short communication to accompany the tool has been drafted. Active development of the tool is nearing completion and we are currently seeking web-space to host the tool, aiming to do so through collaboration within the consortium and wider EJP. Continuing updates to the contents of the tool are carried out through ‘show and tell’ sessions at consortium meetings.

JIP2-WP2-T3: Knowledge transfer and dissemination (M25-M35)

Different dissemination activities of WP2 have taken place during the OHEJP ASM; an oral presentation and a poster both related to the development of the guideline in WP2.1. Also an oral presentation on the guidelines during the World One Health Conference was given.

An important element of this workpackage is the actual use of the guidelines developed in WP2.1. The guidelines focus on implementation and operationalization. The idea is to have pilots in several European countries to start with implementing or strengthening the collaboration between the

human-veterinary-food domain in the area of signaling, risk assessment, response and control of zoonoses. By doing that during the project experiences within the pilots could feed back to further improve the guidelines. However, due to COVID-19 the progression which was on scheme was stopped abruptly. The pilot countries are Norway, Portugal, Italy and Belgium. After setting the goal and performance of a stakeholder analysis Belgium was ready for step 3, the systems mapping workshop. This workshop should have taken place on March 27, but was cancelled a few days in advance. After trying to postpone to June, the new aim was to have it in October. However, due to the changing COVID-19 situation in Belgium it turned out not to be possible after all and it is further delayed. Also, the other pilots were strongly hampered by the COVID-19 crisis. However, Norway managed to make a draft systems map and performed a stakeholder analysis. Italy and Portugal have done the first part of the stakeholder analysis online. Since the prospects are not very positive and travel seems not to be feasible at a short term, we decided to try to organize a systems mapping workshop in which the participants are physically present as well as the local moderators, but the lead will be done virtually from Swiss. The first country who will try this approach is Norway, most likely followed by Belgium. Hopefully, we will manage to perform the first 3 steps (setting goal, stakeholder analysis and systems mapping) in all four pilot countries. These experiences will be used to improve the guidelines. Unfortunately, hardly any time will be left for the following steps, reducing the impact of these show cases for other countries.

WP3: Towards an EU zoonoses structure

JIP2-WP3-T1: Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis (M1-M24)

The task focuses on identifying factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals of zoonotic events within and between countries. During a workshop in Uppsala in 2019 the focus of the task was set to identify different factors that contribute to well-functioning systems or ways to share signals as well as factors that prevent sharing of signals, both within and between countries, focusing on the persons in the systems rather than the technical or organizational solutions. In depth semi-structured interviews were considered to capture more in-depth information than a written questionnaire. Interviews of persons working within food safety, public health and veterinary medicine at central, regional or local level were performed in six countries. COVID-19 has affected some of the interviews.

The first round of national data analysis has been completed although COVID-19 has delayed the analysis. Performing the joint thematic analysis was planned as an activity done in physical meeting, but was turned into a virtual one. In general, the participating countries have experienced that they through the interviews have received new information which is relevant when understanding signal sharing. Several themes identified were common for the participating countries, and some of the findings were even surprisingly similar between countries. One theme that was mentioned by a majority of the participants was the importance of knowing someone in person, which was described as a prerequisite for informal contacts which are often used for signal sharing. Other themes were: 1) the need for formal structures for sharing signals (e.g. legislation, clear routines) which was not in contrast to the personal contacts – both are needed, 2) further need for understanding of the mandates of persons working in different sectors, 3) prioritization can be affected by prior knowledge and experience, 4) the technical (IT) systems can be beneficial but several examples were given of outdated systems, parallel systems or systems not accessible between sectors, 5) legal restrictions for sharing data was described as a hinder for signal sharing, 6) concern or fear of overreaction by the

recipient of the signal and concern or fear for leakage of the information were concerns raised in relation to signal sharing.

Based on the findings, the following preliminary recommendations have been developed: 1) Acknowledge the importance of personal contacts and ensure that there are occasions when people can see each other (eg regular meetings) or collaborate to learn to know each other. 2) Make sure there are structures in place, and understanding for each other's roles and mandates. 3) Strive for well-functioning cross-sectional technical systems, make it possible to share and access data.

Two presentations were given at the OHEJP annual conference in Prague, one oral presenting the results from the Italian part of the study, and one poster describing the whole project. The work drafting the manuscript has continued. Further, another project, close to Task 3.1, was presented for the DG Santé in January 2020 while they performed an audit in Sweden on “Early detection and notification systems in place for emerging animal diseases”. The representatives from DG Santé were very interested in the study and in the preliminary findings presented. The results from 3.1 have also been presented for working groups within the OHEJP-project Matrix.

JIP2-WP3-T2: Horizon Scanning Pilot Exercise (M1-M24)

The pilot horizon scanning exercise that took place in November 2019 was based on an assembly of information sources and an assembly of analysis teams with assigned topics. Within task 3.2 a horizon scanning team composed of experts within public health, animal health, food safety has been established. To explore the potential application of such a technique, the pilot exercise first identified more than 30 potential One Health issues. From these a summary of six drivers were identified to have a key impact in the next coming years: political and decision making behaviour, people and consumer behaviour, science and innovations, market behaviour, new and re-emerging pathogens or threats and climate change. The conducted pilot horizon scanning exercise showed to be useful but needs to be further developed for foresight applications related to One Health in Europe. The One Health pilot horizon scanning exercise took place (Nov 2019) prior to the covid-19 pandemic. Even though the foresight was focused on One Health the exercise identified many issues that have been of relevance during the last months. The task leader participated in a horizon scanning exercise organised by the WHO, using similar methodology. A scientific report on the horizon scanning exercise is in progress. The results were presented in a poster at the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting in May 2020.

JIP2-WP3-T3: Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (M6-M30)

The aim of this task is to learn from past experiences with respect to zoonotic outbreaks. Hantavirus and Q-fever in the UK were chosen to be retrospectively analyzed. All UK-government publications relating to Hantavirus and Q-fever have been compiled and their data-sources tracked and mapped. After this, all data gathered from the November 2019 workshop has been used to map One-Health surveillance structures for Q-fever into a general European map from consortium partners. Cross-comparing these has identified the ‘common core’ of components that are present in all those countries. Due to COVID-19 work on this component paused in mid-March but has since resumed. Collaboration with participants in refining, adding detail and finalising the One Health structures in each country is still required, and is significantly delayed by COVID-19. In tandem, a map of Q-fever surveillance protocols in the UK veterinary sector has been made to identify local strengths and weaknesses. We hope to expand this across public health and food safety in the UK.

JIP2-WP3-T4: Pilot One-Health Early Warning System (M25-M36)

The core feature of this pilot was originally envisaged to start with a face to face meeting with One-Health professionals across the COHESIVE project. Due to COVID-19 it is unlikely that such a meeting can take place. We have amended the plans to convert this to an online format and are currently focused on identifying One Health representatives in institutes involved in COHESIVE. Aims, objectives and terms of reference will be drafted for the meetings and development of the documents can be carried out online.

There will be additional challenges to developing such a group only online as trust plays a significant part in open sharing of information and ideas, this may slow the effective development of such a group and will require innovative approaches. Unfortunately due to the ongoing highly pathogenic avian influenza outbreak across Northern Europe the online meeting had to be postponed to early 2021 due to limited availability of animal health colleagues. However the network already formed through the COHESIVE project has been collaborating individually around sharing, country specific, risk assessments on HPAI H5N8.

JIP2-WP3-T5: Development of a tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis (CBA) (M25-36)

Due to COVID-19 work on this task has not progressed as much as originally planned as key staff members have been redirected to COVID-19 related activities. An email was circulated to the whole COHESIVE project seeking active contributions to the task. A number of positive responses were received. An abstract for a poster was accepted to the EJP ASM also looking to recruit more members to the project however the revised online format of the meeting made this less effective than hoped. Current work is focused on performing a systematic review of cost-benefit analysis studies within the foodborne zoonosis remit. This will incorporate input from other OHEJP members in order to gather CBA experience from across the OHEJP consortium. The systematic review will culminate in a framework for optimizing CBA studies. Work on the literature review is continuing and preliminary results were discussed at the recent COHESIVE annual meeting. The discussion session highlighted a number of areas where the literature search terms could be improved.

WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

JIP2-WP4-T1: Molecular typing data and metadata – database creation

The feasibility studies on the three Member States (The Netherlands, Italy, Norway) are ongoing. Three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) are online and have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. RIVM and WBVR of The Netherlands have provided details of their coding systems. They are currently under the harmonization phase. In particular, RIVM has produced the coding systems for HEV but not yet for *Listeria*. NVI has not produced any coding system for *Listeria* yet. Both delays are somehow related to COVID-19 pandemic. ISS and NRL are conducting a sharing exercise of WGS data and metadata of *Listeria* and STEC using federated information systems. The architecture has been presented at COHESIVE annual meeting. The coding systems have been harmonized. The bioinformatics analysis harmonization is on going.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST5: Filling of DBs (M15-M26)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “*Linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the epidemiological analysis tools*”.
- During the General Meeting on November 2019 in Rome, it was decided to start the activity of integration among the three information systems of the WP4. A telco was planned for

the beginning of 2020 followed by face-to-face meeting. The activity has been affected by COVID-19 crisis. The new plan is to finish the activity by the early months of 2021.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST6: Design and implementation of pipelines (M21-M32)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “*Study of available pipelines*”.
- We are connected with the EJP ORION project, which has a WP specifically dedicated to this activity.
- The activity has been affected by delay of ORION deliverables due to COVID-19 crisis. So far, the deliverable produced by ORION do not describe the details of tools to be used in the pipelines. A new meeting is foreseen with NVI for clarifications.

JIP2-WP4-T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework

JIP2-WP4-T2-ST2 (M1-M32)

In subtask 2, several modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting – in part developed in the framework of other projects - will be unified in one platform – the FoodChain-Lab web application (FCL Web):

- A data collection module
- An interactive analysis module
- A WGS-data integration module
- A reporting module
- A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL)

The overall status and progress of the whole FCL project can be inspected at <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/foodchain-lab>. The specific status and new software versions of the FCL Web are deployed automatically to a test server where new features of the tool can be seen live. Since November 2020, FCL Web is in production mode which accessible at <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>. A revised login procedure including obtaining the user’s consent to gather personal data as well as data security documents was developed. In addition, a JSON-based data exchange format allows for visualising and analysing delivery data obtained from a data collection mask developed in a national project in FCL Web. In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box.

JIP02-WP4-T2-ST3 (M13-M32)

In several presentations on FoodChain-Lab the audience highlighted the importance for integration of WGS data into tracing network visualisations. In addition to the work performed in 2018 and 2019, an interface to the COHESIVE Information System, the whole genome sequencing database mentioned in JIP-WP4-T1 is planned and work will be intensified in the upcoming weeks. This subtask will not be finished as planned until M32 and is prolonged until M40.

JIP2-WP4-T3: Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST1: Requirement analysis (M1-M9)

Typical components have been identified that support quantitative microbiological risk assessment, advanced simulation techniques, documentation and extended usability. Selection of minimal models for testing and development is completed. The prioritization of building blocks for implementation in web application of risk is finished.

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST2 Implementation (M10-M30)

Various minimal models from the literature and from project partners were tested and defined. Risk questions and scenarios as well as quantitative risk models were provided by partners in COHESIVE and other EJP projects. As part of the implementation of standards, we were also provided with data sets and use-cases in cooperation with the FLI. Currently, also the search of models and data suitable as case study (ideally with input from project partners) is ongoing. Due to the corona pandemic we have a delay of 3 months. Furthermore, in cooperation with project partners we have prioritized different building blocks. For the web application of risk we developed various mocks to define the workflow and the individual steps of the user interface in R shiny.

In the first step we have successfully implemented the one-dimensional Monte-Carlo simulation in our web application. The Prototype of “quantitative Riskanalysis” was developed and is finished. With “quantitative Riskanalysis” different risk models can now be implemented and calculated.

The implementation of further statistical methods for quantitative risk assessment is also finished with the support of an external software company.

With our new Shiny app for probabilistic analysis, users can now create and calculate their own mathematical model. The special features of this tool are the data fitting with user-specific data, the evaluation of uncertainties e.g. model uncertainty, scenario uncertainty and item uncertainty as well as a complete documentation of the model which contributes to transparency and reusability of models.

With our Shiny R App "Risk" the user now has the possibility to run one and two dimensional Monte-Carlo simulations via a user friendly interface and to view and document the results.

JIP2-WP4-T4: Dissemination

Although dissemination duties of WP4 achievements start only from M25, a lot of dissemination work for FCL and the tracing portal that was set up in COHESIVE was done in the framework of other projects in the years 2018 and 2019 (workshops and presentations on FCL, meetings with stakeholders). In the framework of COHESIVE annual meetings, presentations and workshops for WP4 tools were conducted for the COHESIVE community.

WP4 activities were presented at the 2020 OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting in an online format (presentation on COHESIVE Information System, poster on FoodChain-Lab Web). In 2021 a joint interactive workshop on WP4 tools and how they interact is envisioned as a satellite event for the COHESIVE final meeting which is open for the COHESIVE community and other interested users. Furthermore, FCL Web will be presented in an interactive virtual event and e learning course in the framework of the One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development module in 2021 (<https://onehealthejp.eu/cpd-2021/>). In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box.

4.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

4.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-1.5	Annual meeting	26	26-11-2020			Since we have had a second meeting with the whole consortium in November 2019, this annual meeting was already postponed to Autumn 2020. Due to COVID-19 we cancelled the physical meeting and changed it into an online annual meeting	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.6	Annual report	28	14-01-2020				4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.7	Closing symposium	42				An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this closing symposium will be postponed to month 42	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-1.8	Annual report	36	21-12-2020				4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-2.5	Development of common procedures and tools	40				An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this deliverable was postponed to month 40.	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-2.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	42				An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this deliverable was postponed to month 42.	8

COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.3	Pathway analysis of exchanging signals	10	21-12-2020			This deliverable was further delayed due to COVID-19. The deliverable is a report on the preliminary results as well as recommendations based on the study has been finalised. Further joint thematic analysis over countries is still ongoing and a manuscript is being drafted. .	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.5	System analysis of detection of outbreaks	24		42		This deliverable had already been extended. Draft of UK systems map completed Dec-2019. Work currently paused due to COVID-19 but has been restarted	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	40				An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this deliverable was postponed to month 42	8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.7	Drivers of change in One Health– a horizon scanning exercise (new deliverable)	30	31-12-2020			New deliverable, not listed in the proposal. A horizon scanning exercise was done at the general meeting in November 2019. Material compiled within WP3.2 (including the exercise) will be compiled.	2,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-3.8	Tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis	42				New deliverable, not listed in the proposal. Started on collating the results of literature review between AGES and APHA, however work is paused due to COVID-19	2,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.1.3	Databases containing the country data	26	30-03-2020			The three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. Details are on the deliverable uploaded to the EJP platform end of March 2020.	4
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.1.4	Description of the pipelines implemented to feed the analysis tools with the data	32		40		Partial information is gathered from involved member states. Pipelines specification will be taken from an ORION deliverable specifically dedicated to	4

		stored in the three databases of this project					this activity. Pipelines integration will start just after ORION deliverable publication. Information was expected to be shared and harmonized among the others softwares from WP4. Covid crisis delayed this point.	
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.2.2	FoodChain-Lab with integrated network analysis module as a web-service browser-ready, open source and implemented in the BfR cloud	32	31.08.2020			FCL Web is already accessible at https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin .	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.2.3	Integration and analysis of epi-data from 4.1 → WGS-Epi module and selected features from IA-1, WP2, WP3	38					4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.3.2	Populating a model project model repository Harmonised graphical user interface prototypes Technical documentation and user guidance	30		39		A public tender for further development of our prototype for quantitative risk analysis was conducted to have some parts of the web application programmed by an external company Due to the corona pandemic and a very long process of the tendering, we have suffered considerable delays.	4,8
COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.3.3	Final testing design elaborated Report section about testing results (internal standards) Report section about testing results using external comparative models) Final release (open access)	40				An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this deliverable was postponed to month 40.	4,8

COHESIVE	D- JIP2-4.4.1	Each subtask conducts workshops, provides documentation and tutorials	42				Deliverable is ongoing and will be continued until the end of COHESIVE in M 42.	4,8
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** Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); Co-creation of common procedures, tools and information to support One Health risk-analysis of zoonoses (national and international)*

4.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.3	Annual report	28	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.4	Closing symposium	42			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this end symposium will be postponed to month 42
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.5	Annual report	36	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.2	Development of common procedures and tools	40			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 40.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.3	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	42			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 42.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.1	Development of common procedures and tools for horizon scanning	26	Yes		A literature review and a report on the workshop and horizon scanning exercise has been finalised.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.2	Pathway and system analysis of signal exchange and outbreak detection	24	Yes		A report on task 3.1 is finalised. The task was delayed partly due to COVID-19.
COHESIVE	M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.3	Local dissemination	42			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 42.

COHESIVE	M-A2.COHESIVE.4.7	Databases containing the country data	26	Yes		The three prototypes information systems (cis-holland, cis-italy, cis-norway) have been filled with information provided by the involved member states. Details are on the deliverable uploaded to the EJP platform end of March 2020.
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.8	Prototype for risk modeling framework ready	30	Yes		Prototype “quantitative riskanalysis” for risk modelling frame is available on github. ChristinWallstab/rrisk-maibornwolff (github.com)
COHESIVE	M-A2.COHESIVE.4.9	Availability of the pipelines from the databases to the analysis tools	40			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 40.
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.10	Analysis of epi-data into tracing framework enclosed	40			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 40.
COHESIVE	M-A2. COHESIVE.4.11	Final release of risk modeling framework	40			An extension of 6M months has been granted. Therefore, this milestone was postponed to month 40.

4.4. Publications and additional outputs

No peer reviewed publications yet.

Additional output

WP2 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague 27-29 May, 2020

Oral presentation:

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion

Frank Koenen, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Frits Vlaanderen, Ines Mogami, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Rosangela Tozzoli, Kitty Maassen on behalf of the COHESIVE WP2 consortium

Poster presentation:

COHESIVE: Understanding the needs for European implementation guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonoses

Ines Mogami-Asselin, Caroline Ribeiro, Malin Jonsson, Frank Koenen, Ewa Pacholewicz, Bart Regeer, Hendrik-Jan Roest, Simon Rüegg, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Frits Vlaanderen, Cecilia Wolff, Kitty Maassen
WP3 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague

WP3 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague 27-29 May, 2020

Oral presentation:

Factors affecting signals sharing of zoonotic events: a qualitative exploratory study in Italy

Michele Luca D'Errico, Maria Nöremark, Chiara Cattaneo, Rosangela Tozzoli, Gaia Scavia

Poster presentation:

To share or not to share - the exchange of signals of zoonotic events within and between countries in Europe

Maria Nöremark, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Charlotte Cook, Michele Luca D'Errico, Rob Dewar, Gry Marysol Grøneng, Malin E Jonsson, Trude Marie Lyngstad, Ines Mogami Asselin, Karin Nyberg, Ewa Pacholewicz, Gaia Scavia, Barbara Schimmer, Cecilia Wolff, Elina Lahti

Poster presentation:

Horizon scanning pilot exercise regarding One Health

Rickard Knutsson, Elina Lahti, Renata Karpiskova, Ivana Kolackova, Ludovico Pasquale Sepe, Rosangela Tozzoli.

WP4 Presentations at the OHEJP annual meeting in Prague

Oral presentation:

cgDIST: a new methodology to inferring phylogeny

Adriano Di Pasquale, Iolanda Mangone, Antonio Rinaldi

Poster presentation:

The COHESIVE Information System: a cross EJP projects example

Adriano Di Pasquale, Fernanda Dorea, Karin Lagesen, Francesca Cito, Alessio Di Lorenzo, Paolo Calistri, Kitty Maassen

Poster presentation:

The FoodChain-Lab Web application – an integrative tracing tool to analyse complex global food supply chains in foodborne crises

Marion Gottschald, Birgit Lewicki, Alexander Falenski, Marco Rügen, Isaak Gerber, Dominic Tölle, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Armin A. Weiser

Abstracts can be accessed from the proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. <https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/D3.12-OHEJP-ASM-2020-Abstract-book.pdf>

WP2 Presentations at the World One Health Conference in Edinburgh 30 Oct - 3 November 2020

Oral presentation:

COHESIVE: Development of implementation guidelines to support countries with early warning, response and control of (emerging) zoonoses in a One Health fashion

Frank Koenen, Sandra Cavaco Gonçalves, Solveig Jore, Charlotte Cook, Elina Lahti, Karin Nyberg, Malin Jonsson, Frits Vlaanderen, Ines Mogami, Mathilde Uiterwijk, Gaia Scavia, Kitty Maassen (presenting author)

Poster presentation:

European guidelines for a One Health Risk Analysis System for zoonotic diseases: a needs assessment using implementation theory

Mogami Asselin, Gonzalez Ines Kuniko; dos Santos Ribeiro, Carolina; Jonsson, Malin; Koenen, Frank; Pacholewicz, Ewa; Regeer, Barbara J.; Roest, Hendrik-Jan; Rüegg, Simon R.; Uiterwijk, Mathilde; Vlaanderen, Frits; Wolff, Cecilia; Maassen, Catharina B.M.; On behalf of WP2 COHESIVE, Part of One Health EJP

4.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

In WP2.1 there are regular meetings with **FAO** and **WHO** in relation to their TZG and our guideline to help one another with tools and experiences. Also to align the initiatives and prevent overlap. Several COHESIVE tools are (to be) included in the SISOT tool box from the Tripartite.

Co-operation with other EJP projects, such as **NOVA** and **ORION**. Within WP2.1 an online glossary is under development together with ORION and NOVA. Within WP4.1.6 there is a complementary collaboration with ORION. In WP4.2 there is a close collaboration with **EFSA** with focus on tracing solutions in the framework of an EFSA-BfR Framework Partnership Agreement. Also, FCL was part of joint **ECDC-EFSA** crisis trainings. There are also links to the EJP **NOVA** project in which a module for analysis of sales data should be integrated into FCL On the national level, FCL is involved in a project with the German federal state North-Rhine Westphalia on developing a data entry mask for supply chain data. Several modules of the tracing portal were developed in the framework of these projects and the aim of COHESIVE is to unify all of them under one umbrella – the FCL tracing portal. In October 2020 in the framework of a **MedVetNet** short term mission, a guest scientist from Istituto Superiore di Sanità in Italy who is also involved in NOVA WP2 and COHESIVE WP3 visited BfR to learn more about tracing and FCL as well as FCL Web. In 2020 FCL Web became part of the SISOT tool box initiated by **OIE, WHO and FAO**. Within task 3.1 there are links to a task within NOVA on early detection and notification of transmissible animal diseases.

In WP4.1 there is a close collaboration with ORION to integrate ontologies on the prototype COHESIVE Information system (CIS). The project EJP **BeOne** is interested to work on top of this result.

Additional contacts are made with **Matrix** and **Televir**. The two EJP projects are evaluating to build their activities upon results from the Cohesive information system.

4.6. Data Management Plan

The DMP of COHESIVE can be found on the OHEJP website in the DMP group. At the end of the project all data are fulfilling the FAIR principle. These include models of which also documentation and codes fulfill the FAIR principle. In 2021 the DMP will be checked for missing information and action will start to make sure the DMP is complete by the end of the project.

4.7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of Ethical Reviewers, January 2018	Project's measures and actions taken at the end of 2018	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2019	Comments Project Leaders, end of 2019	Comments of Ethics Advisors, January 2020	Comments Project Leaders, mid-2020	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020
none	none	none	none	Nothing Pending - Closed	N/A	N/A

4.8. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	COVID

Additional information

Some indicated risks already led to delays (see previous reports). The major current problem is COVID-19. This leads to delay in work plan execution as well as to delay in duties, tasks and reporting. This was already the case, before COVID-19. The combination might lead to not making all deliverables or with lower quality than expected. The main reasons are the reduced availability of (key)personell and travel restrictions

Several modules to be integrated into the tracing portal are developed in the framework of other projects. However, if such a project fails to develop a usable module, the respective module cannot be integrated into the COHESIVE tracing portal

4.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	OHEJP annual meeting: 3 oral presentations and 5 poster presentations		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	750	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	Yes		

Name of the activity:	Presentation on COHESIVE in 6 th stakeholders committee meeting with oa EFSA, ECDC, WHO, FAO, OIE		
Date:	12 Oct 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	17	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	8		

Name of the activity:	World One Health Conference; 1 oral presentation, 1 poster presentation		
Date:	30 Oct – 3 Nov 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	>1000	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	yes		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Continuing Professional Development module: outbreak preparedness		
Date:	16-17 Nov 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	Yes	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	27	Media	
Industry	1	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Presentation on COHESIVE in coghwheel workshop Safeconsume		
Date:	25 Nov 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	20	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	COHESIVE annual meeting		
Date:	24 and 26 Nov 2020		
Place:	Virtual event		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	4		

Name of the activity:	Italian National Reference Centre GENPAT – Annual national workshop		
Date:	25/11/2020		
Place:	Virtual		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	80	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

5. JIP3 - CARE

5.1. Summary of the work carried out

In the reporting period of year 3 (12M), the EJP CARE has progressed, more or less as planned and according to agreed work plan, meeting most of the deliverables and milestones in time with only a few amendments due to Covid-19.

The consortium agreement D.0.1 was finalized and put in force in the early days of the project kick off (D0.4). The coordination runs smoothly with scheduled virtual meetings between the two lead organizations as well as among the WP leads every 14 days and all partners every quarter. Additional virtual meetings have been conducted within each of the WPs to ensure compliance to the work plan and discussion of risks and contingency planning. The progress is monitored in detail in a comprehensive way with bi-monthly reporting by the WP lead using a developed monitoring framework (D.0.2).

The two lead organizations have participated in all activities organized by the OHEJP WP4 promoting and disseminating information about the OHEJP and related activities including the development of the dissemination plan (D.0.3). All reports, documents, deliverables etc. are shared among the partners in a designated DTU share site. In addition are all deliverables deposit in the OHEJP group site and public deliverables in Zenodo. The two lead organizations have implemented a quality control system of finalized deliverables by including a review board mechanism where WP1 review deliverables of WP2 and WP3 review WP4 and vice versa. Most deliverables have timely been uploaded to Zenodo.

A mapping review has been conducted identifying available and existing External Quality Assurance (EQA) programs offered to the National Reference Laboratories for zoonotic bacterial agents including antimicrobial resistance (AMR) from both the public health and veterinary side embracing the One Health concept (D.1.1). The mapping review will serve as a guidance in setting up new EQA scheme expanding to whole genome sequencing (WGS) which for many laboratories in the EU is still a novel technology and approach. The scope is also to assess if EQAs could be facilitated in a jointly way using the same reference material across the EQA providers for assessing the quality of testing zoonotic bacterial agents including antimicrobial resistance.

The pilot EQAs are unfolding following the plans but with some delays. The EQA on isolation, detection and characterization of pathogens were extensively elaborated both during the kick off but also most of year 3. The plan has finally been accepted by the partners and WP leads and with delays being initiated in year 4. The 2nd EQA on typing/characterization including WGS has similarly been delayed. The lost time will likely be intercepted as the genomes of the reference material currently being closed after signing MTAs. The 3rd of the EQAs on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data progresses nicely with a genomic data almost finalized including outbreak genomes in a suitable background. The associated case description is being finalized as well serving to guide the participants for the simulated outbreak investigation based on a genomic cluster analysis to mimic a real scenario.

Progress has also been observed identifying the priority pathogens for which reference material should be collected. A list of nine pathogens, all known to be responsible for foodborne human infections, were agreed upon among the WP2 partners. The target list will serve as a basis for which gaps will be identified in available reference material to cover all known serotypes, genotypes and generally pathogenic variants of the selected pathogens

which are relevant for human health, also including AMR mechanisms and associated metadata within the nine pathogens completing a repository/database of reference material. A questionnaire was disseminated to inquire CARE partners about available reference material. A large number of available reference materials was reported (D.2.1) and process to acquire these is ongoing with the aim to Whole Genome Sequence them, if not already available as genomes, to provide typing/characterization including AMR determinants. Thus, the bioinformatics tool, ResFinder was updated and available in a version 4.1 enabling the above analysis (D.2.2) which has been postponed to Dec. 2021.

A webinar was conducted to shed more light on the Nagoya protocol for compliance by the WP2 which will look after to get in touch with National focal point officers. During the kick-off meeting WP2 and WP3 discussed how to enable the use of and visibility of the reference material repository/database with a mutual agreement on the structure of the repository/database. This was further elaborated through a questionnaire survey conducted, assessing also the Microbial Resources research Infrastructure (MIRRI) database structure. The final agreement and layout of the reference material database structure catalogue was delivered (D.3.1.1), followed by the synthesis document listing partner expectations, a list of existing software and technical choice (D.3.1.2).

The planned risk assessment activities have gained speed and momentum identifying initially whom to be surveyed including the target audience from the EFSA network for microbial risk assessment. A small literature review was conducted to establish criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility in the field of risk assessment. The target group of risk assessors was approached with a developed questionnaire to query criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility as well as what type of risk assessment data and associated data to record (D.4.1.1). The outcome allowed WP4 to establish a roadmap for sharing information for pathogens and AMR useful for exposure/risk assessment with already established and existing other initiatives (D.4.1.2).

In summary, the CARE project progresses more or less as planned reaching milestones and deliverables in time. CARE has only moderately been affected by Covid-19, thus, only required minor amendments.

5.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP0 Coordination

WP0-T1 Over-all project coordination

DTU and SSI constitute the management team and has established a comprehensive management system to ensure that all deliverables and milestones for the vast of the majority are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project and submitted using the designated OHEJP format. DTU are hosting the secretariat, which are essential to the successful completion of the proposed work programme. Furthermore, DTU has set up and are hosting a CARE share site for storage of all reports, deliverables, milestones, minutes and other documentation produced as part of CARE.

In February, DTU and SSI organized and facilitated the CARE kick off meeting held at both DTU and SSI in Denmark as part of Sub-Task JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1-ST1: Organize kick off meeting (M.0.1). The kick off meeting allowed all partners to be acquainted with the objective, recommendation from the SSB and discuss the content of the work-plan. The minutes of the kick off meeting were reported and shared in the share site (D.0.4). During the preparatory work of CARE, DTU facilitated and sealed the consortium agreement (D.0.1) as well as the dissemination plan (D.0.3).

CARE status meetings for the management team (DTU and SSI) has been conducted every second week. Furthermore, DTU and SSI has organized and conducted work package (WP) lead virtual meeting every 14 days to inform, discuss and delegate news / tasks from the OHEJP WPs as part of Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1 Over-all project coordination. In addition, to feedback from each of the WP leads as to progress, deliverables, delays etc. Minutes of all meetings have been reported and shared at the CARE share site. In continuation of the management of the progress, bi-monthly reports (internal progress reporting templates) (D.0.2) are requested from the WP leads in which they report WP progress, deliverables etc. These reports are also stored in the share site. The management team has enforced the WP leads to provide high quality work why a review system has been implemented where WP1 review the work of WP3 and WP2 the work of WP4 and vice versa.

The management team has organized and conducted joint partner virtual meetings every quarter allowing to disseminate information not shared already by email but primarily to allow the 16 partners to provide a feedback to progress and accomplishments. Minutes of these meeting are also reported and saved in the share site.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element and the list of data covered in CARE was specified during the first year of the project. It covers data from collection to availability and longterm storage. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. Also, the management of the data is discussed proactively and the DMP is regularly discussed with the WP-leaders and the CARE consortium during the project.

The DMP itself was compiled using a specific tool provided by the OHEJP: Collaborative Data Platform (CDP). The access to the first version of the DMP was finished, M33. The CARE Deputy Leader from SSI is responsible for the CARE DMP and contributions from all participants. The final DMP will be published at the end of the project lifetime. First version of DMP (2020) includes three research datasets are listed below and in the first version of CARE DMP linked to a Dataset ID:

- A survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment Dataset ID: JIP-3-WP4-1
- List of resources relevant information for risk assessment Dataset ID: JIP-3-WP4-2

- Inventory of available RM for several purposes (PT trials, quality control, validation, experimental methods. Dataset ID: JIP-3-WP2-1-EUROPANELOH

WP1 Develop of cross-sectional PT's (proficiency testing)

The overall aim of WP1 is to develop PT schemes that can be used to assess the combined performance of the OH sector, i.e. the human, food/feed, and veterinary sectors. The WP are divided into three tasks.

WP1-T1 Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes

The activity was completed in M32 with the publishing of a report: D1.1. Mapping of existing and proposals for new Proficiency Tests / External Quality Assurance schemes on the EJP-CARE sharpshoot site.

The purpose T1 was to map the currently available PT schemes and to identify existing and propose new PT schemes that can be used in a cross sectorial context. Lucas Wijnands and Kirsten Mooijman RIVM (NL) was the responsible partner on the task. The report was developed through a series of TC's where drafts were discussed and further elaborated, resulting in a final version, that were approved by all partners. The report summarizes the usefulness of the available PT's from a OH perspective and concludes that none of the existing PTs/EQAs cover all the different sectors. Therefore, new PTs/EQAs have to be developed covering the veterinary, food and human health sectors. It is suggested in the report that the focus of the PT's should be on new molecular, preferably WGS-based, methodologies, that are being used cross-sectorial. The areas covered should include both wet and dry laboratory procedures, and include detection of pathogens in primary materials and methods used for characterization of isolates.

The conclusions from the report are in line with the work that originally was proposed in the main application from the EJP-CARE consortium, and the report provides a roadmap for the work in WP1-T2, where the aim is to conduct pilot PT's to support the development of new cross sectorial PT schemes.

WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome (start month 31)

The aim of WP1-T2 is to conduct a pilot PT that can support the developing of new PT schemes that can be used to assess the combined performance of the OH sector. The work is organized in three subtasks with the following leads:

- WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens, Lead: Elina Lathi, SVA (SE), co-lead Cecilia Jernberg, FHM (SE).
- WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS, Lead: Rene Hendriksen, DTU (DK) (SE) co-lead Kees Veldman WBVR (NL).
- WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data Lead: Jeppe Boel, SSI (DK), co-lead Nick Coldham, APHA (UK).

The planning of the three pilot PT's is well underway and the three pilots will be executed in the first half of Y 4. The planning of the PT's have been spearheaded by the leads and co-leads of the three subtasks, and discussed in TC's. The PT participants will primarily be members of the CARE consortium and the recruitment of laboratories are in progress. The current plans and status of the three subtask are:

WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

The aim of this pilot PT is to increase the understanding of the cross-sectorial capabilities to detect and characterize food-borne pathogens in a matrix relevant to the sectors of food safety, veterinary medicine and public health.

The laboratories participating in the pilot PT can be participants of the EJP CARE project or laboratories situated in a country that is participating in the One Health EJP. The participant can, if relevant, use an external commercial laboratory or a regional or local counterpart, as a contractor if the methods for a specific pathogen within the panel are not a part of the routine analyses of the participant. Information on methods used should then be collected from the contracted laboratory. The PT consists of five samples containing freeze-dried cultures of target pathogens *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella* and *Yersinia* and five e-swabs. The vials will contain one to three of the target pathogens as well as a negative sample with no target pathogens. The vials might also include non-target background bacteria. The PT will be launched in April in Y4. The participating laboratories will be requested to detect and characterize the target pathogens to species level (*Campylobacter*), to serovar level (*Salmonella*) and to species and biotype level (*Yersinia*) according to the methods routinely used by each laboratory. The laboratories may choose to participate in the detection and characterization of all three target pathogens or one or two of them.

WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS (CARE genomic PT)

In past evaluations of the EU Reference Laboratory (EURL) system, the lack of synergies in the provided external quality assurance schemes across the EURLs have been raised and possible actions have been requested. In the CARE pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS it is the aim to address this issue by jointly using the same reference material for EQA providers both the veterinary and public health sector laboratories to assess the reported results of the typing and characteristics for quality and comparability.

The PT will assess the quality and comparability of WGS based on a set of WGS quality metrics and look into the laboratories ability to detect and assign subtypes/attributes from WGS data from bacterial isolates e.g. sero- and sequence types, antimicrobial resistance genes, toxin subtypes etc. The aim is to assess both the individual and the collective performance of the partner participating laboratories.

The reference material provided to the laboratories will be from bacteria that are relevant from a one-health perspective, i.e. *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli*. The strains for the PT have been fully characterized and are ready for the PT. For each species both a pure culture of live organisms and pre-prepared extracted DNA will be forwarded as test material. The participating partners shall perform DNA extraction, purification, library-preparation, and WGS of the bacterial cultures. Moreover, to whole-genome-sequence the pre-prepared DNA originating of the same bacterial cultures will be provided. Participants will be requested to submit reads in FASTQ format to a FTP site and submit the identified sequence types, virulence and resistance genes, etc, present in the strains to an informatic IT module. The submitted reads will be evaluated and individual feedback will be provided to each of the participants. The PT will be launched in the spring of Year 4. The partners that provides EQA services will also be granted access to the informatic IT module that can be used to evaluate and compare assigned WGS quality metrics and typing characteristic, including nomenclature on different species. This will enable the EQA providers to evaluate and compare the performance of their own work streams, pipelines, and nomenclature with other partners working within the field of organizing genomic PTs.

W1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance

With this pilot the aim is to develop proficiency testing schemes for the analysis of whole genomes sequence (WGS) data to detect clusters as might be required during an outbreak response. The outbreak exercise will take place over a period of two weeks, where information will be released stepwise and the assignment of the participants is to identify potential outbreak clusters.

The pilot distribution will consist of WGS data files, in FASTQ format, from approximately 100 different isolates. These have been derived from field isolates and include those from *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and salmonellas. A FTP site at SSI will be used to supply the WGS data sets and additional information. Participants will be invited to analyse the data using their current operational pipelines and from phylogenetic analysis report back those which constitute an outbreak cluster of these three species. The participants are expected to receive information up to four times during the exercise and will be notified when new information is available for download. When new information has been analyzed the participants shall report back their results over a LIMs platform. The reported data will be evaluated and compared with the results established by the PT organizers both with regard to cluster identification and response time. The participants will receive individual feedback on their performance.

The participating laboratories will be divided into two groups, one representing the public health side and one representing the food and veterinary side. It is foreseen that participants may wish to perform the outbreak cluster analysis for a single, two, or all three species depending upon their laboratory specialism. The outbreak exercise is planned for May in Y4.

WP1-T3 Development of guidance document with suggestions for design of future cross-sectorial PT schemes (start month 49)

This part of the WP has not started yet.

WP2 Creation of EUROpanelOH, a reference database of strains and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors

WP2-T1 Inventory of current use and existence of reference materials across CARE / OHEJP partner institutes, for selected, prioritized pathogens and antimicrobial resistances

The first time period has developed a minimum set of descriptive standard information to be associated with individual biological resources among CARE partners. During the kick-off meeting, what bacterial pathogens to focus on in CARE was discussed to ensure feasibility. It was agreed to focus on foodborne bacterial pathogens to align with the scope of the partners official reference laboratory designations, thus, a list of priority pathogens was created. These attributes include qualitative characteristics and physical location of the biological resources as well as contact information of the supplier. An inquiry was made for feed-back on the attributes selected by the task leaders. Some additional attributes have been suggested and included in the final excel template of the inventory of resources. Some attributes were considered mandatory information to consider the inclusion of the bacterial strains in the final database, such as the sector of isolation (human, animal, food, feed, environment), year and country of isolation, while some were instead considered as informative. The template was sent to CARE partners on April 27th. The duly filled templates were expected before June 30th. However, because of the critical

sanitary situation in several countries due to the Covid pandemic, the deadline for sending back excel templates that inventoried partners' resources has been extended to September 2020.

A total of 12 partner institutes contributed to the inventory of putative reference materials. Most of them registered more than single pathogens, at least 2 to 3 different pathogens (IP, DTU, SVA, PIWET, IZSAM, IZSLER) to more than 4 to 8 different pathogens (ANSES, UCN, ISS). Finally there were 2960 strains that have been considered as candidates for inclusion (D.2.1). Some of reference materials was provided from EJP OH projects especially in the frame of Listadapt (for *Listeria monocytogenes*) and Tox detect (for *Bacillus cereus*).

The database of resources (D.2.1) was analyzed for the content of information given by the partners. There were only eight strains from which no metadata are available due to confidentiality agreement. Such strains could be used as EQAS materials for dedicated purposes. The compliance with Nagoya protocol regulations has been fully addressed during the inventory timeframe. Countries of origin were unknown or not mentioned for 91 strains. That corresponds to less than 0.03% of the total number of inventoried strains. If the unknown geographical origin of some genetic resources may hamper the future distribution of the strains, it cannot prohibit the handling of the stateless material by CARE partners. Of course the use and full characterization of such resources will not be favored in the next phases. It is worth noting that access to the Spanish and French resources will necessitate authorizations from the two National Focal point services.

WGS data are already available for some strains and species. This is not enough however to create the sub-database for antimicrobial resistances as initially planned. Indeed, WGS data are available for 66% *Listeria* strains, 43% *Campylobacter* strains, 83% *Bacillus* strains, 25% *Salmonella* strains, 24% *E. coli* strains and 15% *Yersinia* strains. Only four strains were fully WGS characterized for *Staphylococcus* and none for *Vibrio* and *Streptococcus*. The AMR sub-database (D.2.2) is therefore postponed to December 2021. It will be set up as genome sequencing will progress by using a unique bioinformatics tool (ResFinder) for resistance gene detection. DTU has worked on updating ResFinder to enable and address the need for having a single standardized database that contains all validated AMR genes classified by mechanisms. That will help for full achievement.

WP2-T2 Gap analysis with respect to accessibility, quality and usefulness of existing and potential new reference materials from a One-Health perspective

The task 2 has begun by sending a letter to all CARE partners for calling experts who will select the reference materials in the database of resources. They will provide rapidly a need's assessment document for conducting the gap analysis in terms of strains and associated information. It is indeed one of the major purposes of CARE to establish a trustable link between the phenotypes and the genotypes of the strains at the final round of integration in EUROpanelOH.

WP2-T3 Production of additional RM to fill in gaps and/or improve characterization if needed

This task will follow in due time when task being a prerequisite has been completed.

WP2-T3-ST1 WGS characterization

This task will follow in due time when task being a prerequisite has been completed.

WP2-T3-ST2 MALDI-TOF characterization

This task will follow in due time when task being a prerequisite has been completed.

WP2-T3-ST3 Completing metadata and phenotypic data

This task will follow in due time when task being a prerequisite has been completed.

WP3 Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

WP3-T1 Development of an information system for making RM more widely accessible and visible

The past year has allowed the construction of the minimum dataset that must be associated with the living Reference Materials (RMs) of the CARE catalog in order for them to be useful as biological standards and compliant with regulations (D.3.1.1)(slightly delayed). The work carried out between the partners has also allowed the definition of the principles for the construction of the Information System (IS) that will host the CARE's catalog of RMs and allow their visibility and distribution (D.3.1.2)(slightly delayed). The choice was made to build a relational database that will be built using the commercial Biologics system, which is the standard chosen by the pan-European MIRRI consortium and appeared to be a realistic solution for having a functional system within the CARE project timeframe. The system will be built by INRAE teams and a first operational version should be delivered in October 2021 (D.3.13). The process of recruiting a person in charge of the development of the CARE's catalog database and of the associated web portal has been initiated (advertising and interviews) and should make it possible to recruit in February 2021.

WP3-T2 Ensure the long-term sustainability of RM collections

The objectives of Task 2 to make the living collections of reference material sustainable have been the subject of preliminary discussions among CARE partners. Several key points were raised, notably on the important role that official MicroBiological Resource Centers (mBRCs INRAE-CIRM & Institut Pasteur-CRBIP) could play in achieving this objective, the question of compliance with the ABS rules of the Nagoya protocol and the interest of collecting living collections on a limited number of sites to allow for efficient distribution according to the mBRCs rules defined by the OECD. The definition of realistic solutions will still have to be discussed next year with the partners, involving their stakeholders (ministries) who are most often the official owners of the biological resources. On the other hand, the choices that will be made on the physical sites for the conservation of the collections will have important consequences on the architecture of the information system, particularly with regard to functionalities related to data curation, data updating and ordering/distribution of reference materials. This is therefore an important issue to be discussed at the level of project coordination.

WP3-T3 Ensuring the long-term accessibility of the RM collection and its existence

Discussions have been initiated with the MIRRI consortium for exposition of the CARE catalog through the MIRRI webportal.

WP4 Investigate, benchmark and improve the availability and the quality of the existing data relevant for risk assessment

WP4-T1 Data and metadata available for risk assessment

WP4 CARE members first established the list of targeted institutes to who the survey was

addressed. This list comprised EJPOH members as well as members from EFSA Microbiological Risk Assessment Network. A small literature review was done to establish criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility in the field of risk assessment.

A draft survey dedicated to collection information on data availability for risk assessment was designed, tested and sent to the list of risk assessors. The survey has been addressed through an online questionnaire

(https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/formation7/questionnaire_RA/questionnaire.htm)

At the end of 2020, the detailed information related to data used in different types of risk assessment was collected for 20 cases.

In the perspective to establish the roadmap for sharing information for pathogens and AMR useful for exposure/risk assessment, a contact was established with other initiatives.

The CARE's objective has been presented to the JIP ORION and RAKIP projects. At the end of 2020, the WP3 lead has initiated the process of reaching out and establishing a stronger connect to the projects ORION and RAKIP for further collaboration.

WP4-T2 Metadata web platform

No specific tasks have been carried out related to task 2 during Y3.

WP4-T3 Dissemination plan

No specific tasks have been carried out related to task 3 during Y3.

5.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

5.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
CARE	D.0.1	Consortium agreement	M25	June 2020			Confidential (is available on the OHEJP website under the CARE group)	8 (Management)
CARE	D.0.2	Internal progress reporting templates	M26	June 2020			Confidential (is available on the OHEJP website under the CARE group)	8 (Management)
CARE	D.0.3	Dissemination plan	M28	June 2020			Public (is available on the OHEJP website under the CARE group and on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/record/3922039#.YAmMNOBFyUk))	8 (Management)
CARE	D.0.4	Minutes of the kick off meeting - 2020	M26	June 2020			Public (is available on the OHEJP website under the CARE group and on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/record/3899901#.YAmMcUBFyUk))	8 (Management)
CARE	D.05	Minutes of the interim meeting 2021	M38					

CARE	D.1.1	WP1-T1: Report - Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes	M30	Sep 2020			Public (is available on the OHEJP website under the CARE group and on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/record/4384713#.YAmMUUBFyUk))	8 (Survey)
CARE	D.2.1	Shared database gathering all information	M34	Nov 2020			The report has been validated by WP4 lead and disseminated	3
CARE	D.2.2	Sub-database for antimicrobial resistances	M35	Postponed	Dec 2021	Yes		3
CARE	D.3.1.1	Database Structure for RM catalog	M32	Aug., 2020 Final v. Dec,2020			Confidential https://share.dtu.dk/sites/EJP_CARE_440200/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?sourcedoc=/sites/EJP_CARE_440200/Deliverables%20and%20milestones/WP3/D3.1.1%20-%20Database%20structure%20for%20reference%20materials%20catalog.xlsx&action=default	4
CARE	D 3.1.2	Synthesis Documents after questionnaire processing 1/ partners expectations 2/	M35	Nov., 2020 Final v. Dec,2020			Confidential https://share.dtu.dk/sites/EJP_CARE_440200/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?sourcedoc=/sites/EJP_CARE_44	8 (Survey)

		list of existing softwares 3/ technical choice					0200/Deliverables%20and%20milestones/WP3/WP3%20D3.1.2%20-%20Final.docx&action=default	
CARE	D.4.1.1	A survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment	M31	September 2020			CO (can be accessed for EJP members https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/formation/7/questionnaire_RA/questionnaire.htm)	8 (Survey)
CARE	D.4.1.2	The establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place	M35		January 2021	Yes	Some interviews with other projects has not been realized in 2020 (e.g. EJP RADAR)	8 (Survey)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

5.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
CARE	M.0.1	Kick off meeting - 2020	M25	Yes		This activity was conducted with participation of all partners as well as WP4
CARE	M.1.1	Kick off meeting for WP1	M25	Yes		This activity was conducted during the Project kick off.
CARE	M.1.2	Review of task 1 and description of relevant pilot PTs	M33	Yes		The report is on the sharepoint
CARE	M.2.1	Identification and localization of available RM among CARE and OH-EJP partners	M33	Yes		The process ended on September by the final inventory of 2960 isolates as RM candidates.
CARE	M.3.1.1	Define list of fields for the RM database	M31	Yes		
CARE	M3.1.2	Building questionnaire on expectations of CARE partners for the RM online catalog	M36	Yes		It was considered that a scenario approach submitted to partners would be more effective
CARE	M.4.1.1	Define the list of targeted institutes to who the survey will be addressed	M27	Yes		Based on MRA EFSA network
CARE	M.4.1.2	Definition of criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility	M34	Yes		The criteria for assessing data availability were inserted in the survey. The list of criteria (data quality) might evolve in the next few months.

CARE	M.4.1.3	Definition of types of risk assessment and associated metadata	M28	Yes		QMRA types were defined according to codex definitions. The most commonly stated objectives (associated to risk questions) have been identified.
CARE	M.4.1.4	Test the draft questionnaire of a small panel of risk assessors	M30	Yes		The draft has been tested by RIVM and ANSES during months 31 and 32.
CARE	M.4.1.5	Letter to take contact with JIP/EJP project (Harmony, Matrix, RADAR,...) and other projects (SIGMA, EFSA Knowledge Junction, RAKIP...)	M34	No	M37	Partially reached (some project still to be contacted)
CARE	M.4.1.6	Teleconference of the different partners of these project to check for synergy and to avoid duplication of the work	M35	No	M37	Partially reached (some project still to be contacted)

5.4. Publications and additional outputs

No peer-reviewed publications yet

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)

Additional output

The antibiotic resistance mobilome in biofilms: Bioinformatic strategies. by Sophia Achaibou¹, Elena Buelow, Sean Kennedy¹, Olivier Chesneau², Catherine Dauga¹

IP CARE partner : 1 Biomix Pôle and 2 CIP-CRBIP, Institut Pasteur, Paris, France.

https://jobim2020.sciencesconf.org/data/posters_proceedings.pdf

5.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

EJP CARE interact with the OHEJP WP5, in specific Ludovico Sepe leading WP5. EJP CARE also copy Yves Pascal D. Van Der Stede from EFSA to important communication pieces. Unfortunately, no contact person has been appointed from ECDC despite EJP CARE has addressed this in multiple occasions.

Contacts with Gudrun Overesch who leads WG2 of the project ENOVAT (**COST Action CA18217**). The Action will establish the largest European online database of veterinary pathogens stored by Action Participants and collaborators representing academia and industry (e.g. diagnostic laboratories). This database will include information on already established strain collections as well as pathogens collected prospectively based on research needs, and it will serve as a unique toolbox for refinement and innovation of diagnostics in veterinary microbiology. As a proof of concept, the new database will be exploited during the Action for optimisation of the MALDI-TOF MS technique and for development of new animal- and infection-specific Clinical Break-Points. ENOVAT and CARE databases could be part of EUROpanelOH which would gather and facilitate access to veterinary and foodborne pathogens as European Reference Materials in a One-Health perspective.

In WP4, CARE's members established many links with other European projects (JIP ORION, RAKIP, Pathogènes-in-foods database,...) in order to present CARE's objectives. In 2021, the CARE's objective will be presented as well to JIP COHESIVE and EJP RADAR. The output of the survey on the available data for risk assessment will be presented to the EFSA Microbiological Risk Analysis Network.

5.6. Data Management Plan

1. Have you uploaded a first version of the project's DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?

Yes as part of WP0 we have uploaded a first version of the DMP on the OHEJP specific tool: Collaborative Data Platform (CDP).

2. Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.

The most difficult part of the DMP was to understand what kind of data that was meant to be part of the DMP. We will probably have to adjust our DMP during the project and have already received feedback of the first version that will be used to further develop the CARE DMP. The tool (CDP) itself was not a problem to work in and it will hopefully not be a problem to update the DMP during the CARE project.

5.7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of ethical reviewers in 2020	What measures and actions do you propose?	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020	Comments Project Leaders, January 2021	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2021	Comments Project Leaders, January 2022
<p>Satisfactory ethics self-assessment</p> <p>Well addressed. Comprehensive completed but Nagoya section needs some further clarification.</p>	Please see below.	N/A	N/A		
<p>(1) biological samples</p> <p>However, from the statement on Nagoya compliance, is the CARE team stating that all the biological resources that will or potential will be used in this project that may have been subject to Nagoya have been collected before October 2014 so are not subject to</p>	No, biological resources used in this project will be owned and originate from the partners. Should other biological resources other than that be used, a MTA or NDA be signed to ensure that CARE comply to the Nagoya protocol.	Satisfactory reply. If "other" biological resources are used which fall under Nagoya requirements please update your ethical statement and submit it	If needed when isolates will be considered as Reference Materials, the formal consent of countries that regulate access will be registered, as claimed by our specific Nagoya document.		

Nagoya regulations. The statement was not completely clear in the ethics checklist.					
(2) Health and Safety	N/A	N/A	N/A		
(3) Other Considering the implications of this work and what the CARE team hopes to achieve, are there any potential IPR or data access issues raised by this work? In WP4 who will have access to the “unique web platform”, the text implies only the OHEJP partners? Will all results, datasets and the reference collections “facilitated” through CARE be fully on Open Access? The team implies this in WP3 but can the team reconfirm please, thank you.	There are discussions at DTU if the web platform will be withdrawn from the project. The datasets and the reference collections “facilitated” through CARE will be fully Open Access	Satisfactory reply	N/A		

5.8. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information

Some of the tasks in CARE has been delayed, primarily due to covid as France in a very long time has been in a covid lock down complicating progress and coordination. In addition, a few tasks needed more time and coordination as anticipated to obtain consensus agreement on the focus, direction and content of the tasks. It is however not foreseen to cause overall delays.

The management team has observed a number of partners not being as active as indicated in the proposal. The management team and WP leaders are trying to the best of their abilities to activate these partners but also feel that the EJP system do not have a mechanism build in to enforce this due to the high co-funding.

5.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	Oral Presentation during the ASM Scientific conference		
Date:	27-29 May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	200	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

6. JIP4 – OH-HARMONY-CAP

6.1. Summary of the work carried out

OH-Harmony-CAP (One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants) is a 2.5-year project that aims to 1. collect information on current capabilities, capacities and interoperability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe by developing an indepth OHLabCap survey, 2. the quantitative description of current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols will identify and possibly close the gaps and suggest future studies on how to best detect and characterise food borne pathogens across the One Health sectors.

The OH-Harmony-Cap project began 1st January 2020. The OH-Harmony-Cap project group meeting and Kick Off Meeting (KOM) were hosted by P21-APHA, Addlestone, UK, 21nd-23rd January 2020 and the three main scientific results and outcomes after the first year were:

I. A report (D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2) summarising the results of a pilot survey on the current practices including identification and evaluation of three indicators and associated targets on capabilities, capacities and interoperability on both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level. The results are relevant input for the further development of the OHLabCap instrument. This instrument will be repeatable and sustainable at an EU and on a National level. It will support harmonised data collection and validation on selected food borne pathogens and encourage cross-sectoral communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthening National networks. One new and important observation that emerged during the analysis of the OHLabCap pilot survey was related to adaptability *i.e.*, the capacity and ability to adjust preparedness, methodology and organisation of each laboratory. Year 2020 saw the coming of a new microorganism: The Covid-19 pandemic which illustrated that adaptability is more relevant than ever, and additional focus will be placed on adaptability in the development of the instrument.

II. The first technical report (D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.1) provides description of the current and best practices for sampling and testing for Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* spp. and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp. This information will contribute to the development of harmonised protocols across the different laboratories and different member states in the EU.

III. Collection of laboratory protocols for Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) and *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* which are in use in the EU/EEA laboratories. This will provide an overview of the protocols adopted for the detection, characterisation and typing of the selected pathogens and the outcome will be a list of protocols for the detection, characterisation and typing of the selected pathogens in the EU/EEA NRLs. This collection is the first step to produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of the model pathogens.

6.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

At both the OH-Harmony-Cap kick-off meeting (KOM) and November 11th consortium meeting various outcomes and agreements was decided:

The WP2 survey should consist of one pilot survey, running from M25-M36 followed by an adjusted survey, which will become the OHLabCap. For the pilot survey, ten parasites using EURO-FBP criteria were chosen with the possibility of adjustment after the Y3 pilot survey. Note, originally, the development of the OHLabCap was divided into two pilot surveys targeting the National reference Laboratories (NRLs) and the primary diagnostic services. However, due to time constraints, it was determined, to combine the two pilot surveys into one pilot survey running Y3 followed by an adjusted survey, Y4. This early change prevented further delays.

It was conveyed to all the participants, via email, on April 1st that, a tentative way forward, and as a direct cause of the Covid19 crisis that it would be necessary to make changes to the work plan and time line which would affect and delay the deliverables and milestones in Y3. The changes included: 1. The WP3 questionnaire will be split into four specific questionnaires, based on model organisms, to ensure a better quality response. In addition, the design of the questionnaires should be as quantitative as possible which would simplify the output and analysis. 2. For WP4, a letter to the ECDC Food and Waterborne Diseases and Zoonoses Network (FWD-Network) and to the EURLs for E. coli, AMR and parasites would be drafted in order to expand the collection of protocols. Of note, the collection of WP 4 protocols has ended and the evaluation of the protocols is ongoing. 3. Related to WP2 and WP3, and to ensure timely response we agreed that the pilot survey and questionnaires should be sent to the EFSA and ECDC contact list. However, it was not possible to acquire contact lists from EFSA and ECDC. Therefore, the WP3 questionnaires were sent out via specific networks (September 2020) and the WP2 pilot survey was sent to the consortium (September 7th, 2020). 4. The second OH-Harmony-Cap meeting, in Uppsala, was initially postponed to September 2020. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic it was changed to an online meeting held on November 11th, 2020.

It needs to be noted that after our KOM meeting we were making good progress but that was quickly hampered by the COVID-19 pandemic. Throughout 2020, our primary concern has been to get timely response and data to WP2, WP3, and WP4. The output of WP2 and WP4 feeds directly into WP5; here, we will 1. setup a workshop for communicating and discussing the outcome of the OHLabCap survey conducted in the framework of WP2 and 2. Conduct practical workshops and e-learning activities dedicated to the application of the harmonised protocols developed in WP4.

On the November 11th 2020 consortium meeting it was conveyed to the participants that the Y4 KOM meeting in Rome was cancelled and replaced by an online meeting on January 13th 2021. Changes and challenges to the WP2 Y4 adjusted survey was discussed. In particular, the need to “route” the survey to make it more user-friendly and to include questions incorporating not only capability, capacity, and interoperability but also adaptability. 3. In January 2021, the consortium parasitologists will decide which parasites should be included in the adjusted WP2 survey.

As part of WP2, participants from the Swedish Food Agency (39-SLV) have suggested that we perform an anonymous survey in Y4 specifically targeting the primary laboratories in the food sector. SLV has informed the OH-Harmony-Cap consortium by email on December 17th, 2020 and it will be discussed on January 13th 2021.

WP1 Project coordination

The OH-Harmony-Cap project changed project leader from Flemming Scheutz to Nadia Boisen in April 2020.

JIP04-WP1-T1 : Internal coordination

Progress: As part of the internal engagement it has been important to effectively communicate the progress and status of the project. At the KOM we communicated a common understanding of the roles and responsibilities, output specifics and expectation.

- Formed the OH-Harmony-Cap project group: WP leaders and WP deputy leaders; Nadia Boisen, Flemming, Scheutz, Mélanie Gay, Mónica Oleastro, Rosangela Tozzoli, Morabito Stefano, Patrizia Rossi, Tryntsje Cuperus, Joke van der Giessen, and Declan Bolton
- Several emails to all participants with project overview, status, and decisions
- Frequent conference calls with WP2, WP3, and WP4
- Three conference calls with OH-Harmony-Cap project group
- Conference call with the OH-Harmony-Cap consortium on July 14 and November 11th

JIP04-WP1-T2 : External coordination, outreach and engagement

Progress: As part of the external engagement and to effectively find synergies with other project, disseminate our project, progress and results, OH-Harmony-Cap has participated and presented

- Presented at CARE, KOM on Feb 12-13th of February 2020.
- Presented at the cogwheel workshop between OHEJP and JPIAMR April 28th 2020
- Presented at OHEJPASM2020 May 29th 2020
- Established contact with Mike Catchpole (ECDC) and Frank Boelaert (EFSA). Stayed connected with these key stakeholders; by inviting them to KOM and to comment on surveys and questionnaires
- Reached out to Rachel Chalmers, Head, Cryptosporidium Reference Unit, Public Health Wales for input and collection on Cryptosporidium protocols
- Collaborated with other OHEJP projects, including PARADISE and TOXOSOURCES
- Participation in other OHEJP teleconferences on February 14th, May 20th, May 28th, August 24th, September 8th, December 10th

JIP04-WP1-T3 : Data management

Progress: The project leader participated in the Data Management Platform (CDP) training on July 29th. The list of data covered in OH-Harmony-Cap DMP was specified during the first year of the project. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. Due to the delayed access of the tool the first version of the DMP was finished with minor delay, M33. The first DMP version (D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1) includes four research datasets.

The final DMP will be published at the end of the project lifetime.

JIP04-WP1-T4 : Sustainability

Progress: At this stage, sustainability activities are mainly entailed to external outreach and detailed in JIP4-WP1-T2

WP2 Development of the OHLabCap

WP months: M25-M54. WP Leader: 13-SSI. Deputy WP Leader: 30-RIVM

The aim of WP2 is to develop a benchmarking instrument “OHLabCap”, by surveying OneHealth laboratory interoperability, capacity and performance across EU. The focus will be on the detection and typing of selected priority foodborne pathogens, AMR determinants, and priority parasites across each sector (AH, PH, and FS). The main deliverable will result in the establishment of an OHLabCap instrument that is generic adjustable and sustainable at both an EU and National level.

JIP04-WP2-T1 : Development and testing of the pilot survey

Progress: As mentioned in the summary above the development of a pilot survey, targeting NRLs, was expanded to include the primary diagnostic services (primary sector). This pilot survey, which will later become the OHLabCap, was drafted covering; [1] capability, [2] capacity, and [3] interoperability (JIP04-WP2-T2-S1, S3). The pilot survey covers six priority bacteria and ten priority parasites have been chosen, as model organisms, together with the antimicrobial resistance (AMR) testing of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

They include:

- Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, and *Listeria*.
- *Echinococcus multilocularis*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trichinella spiralis*, *Echinococcus granulosus*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Trichinella* spp. other than *T. spiralis*, *Giardia lamblia*, *Anisakidae*, *Toxocara* spp. and *Taenia solium*

The survey was adapted for the EU online survey tool (JIP04-WP2-T2-S2) and distributed to the OH-Harmony-Cap consortium on September 7th 2020. The results were compiled, analysed and used to prepare Deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.1 ‘Completed Pilot Survey’ and Deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2, “OHLabCap Result of the Pilot survey”

JIP04-WP2-T2 : Scoring of Collected Data and Chosen Indicators

(M31-M36), Task Leader: 32-FHI

Progress: The pilot survey was circulated among the OH-Harmony-Cap consortium (see above). As described in the deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2 the following recommendations for the adjusted survey was derived:

Modifications of the survey questionnaire should include a change in the format into a routed survey. Classification and scoring of indicators by functions measured on capacity, capability, interoperability and communication needs to be clarified. Of particular attention is the inclusion of the “NA” option in many of the questions. This report only presents the combined, general targets and dimensions. The final revised tool should be able to present the target score distribution by discipline (human, animals, food/feed) and dimension scores (for human, animal and food/feed) by country (maps). Furthermore, the OH-Harmony-Cap parasitologists will have to address the question if all 10 parasites should be included in the adjusted survey. It should also be considered if the adjusted survey could include an indicator and associated targets on adaptability *i.e.* the capacity and ability to adjust preparedness, methodology and organisation of each laboratory. Simple indicators could include time frames on when a method was implemented or how long the present organisation has been in place.

Note: adaptability is more relevant than ever due to Covid-19 pandemic, As such, we will collect

information on adaptability in the adjusted survey. The COVID-19 pandemic caused delays in the work. As such, the deliverable, D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2, will be delayed until M38 to ensure that we will be able to include responses that were received after the original deadline.

WP3 One Health Laboratory Interoperability Guidance

WP months: M25-M54. WP Leader: 26-Teagasc. WP Deputy Leader: 36-INSA

JIP04-WP3-T1 : Sampling and Testing

Description of the task: Harmonised testing, including sampling algorithms and laboratory methods for the detection of foodborne pathogens and AMR determinants in food, feed, animal and human samples in Europe. The outputs will include recommendations on a harmonised OH approach, based on the most effective methods currently available, including opportunities offered by new technologies such as WGS.

JIP04-WP3-T1-S1: Establishing current practise (questionnaire)

Progress: Four questionnaires, on STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* were drafted covering; [i] Sampling & testing; [ii] Characterisation of methods and [iii] Data management of harmonised reporting. In the period under review these were adapted for the EU online survey tool and a pilot questionnaire was undertaken. Based on the feedback from participants the original questionnaires were revised and the full survey undertaken. The questionnaire was sent out to and completed by European public health, veterinary and food testing institutions and National Reference Laboratories reached via the European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL), the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Zoonoses networks, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), Food and Waterborne diseases network, among others. The results were compiled, analysed and used to prepare the first subsection of Deliverable 3.1 covering 'Current practice in the EU: Sampling, testing (detection & confirmation)' for each of the target pathogens; Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* spp. and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp.

JIP04-WP3-T1-S2 : Best practice

Progress: The technical report on Sampling and Testing of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. in the European Union (D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.1.) was drafted. This report is divided in sections covering each of the target microorganisms with subsections on current practices, best practices, detection methods and the latest sampling technological developments. As stated above, the information provided on current practices is based on the responses to a questionnaire while the other sections were prepared by experts in the respective areas, with reference to the peer reviewed and other relevant technical literature. After several rounds of review and revision, the final report and deliverable was uploaded onto the OHEJP website, Harmony Group (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/groups/oh-harmony-cap/documents/>) on December 10th, 2020. This document provides important information on current capabilities, capacities and interoperability both at the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level and a description of the current and best practices. It will contribute to the development of harmonised protocols across the different laboratories and different member states in the EU. Moreover, it identifies potential research that should be undertaken in order to improve detection and

characterisation of food borne pathogens across the one health sectors, specifically in sampling and testing for Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* spp. and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp.

WP4 Harmonisation of Protocols

WP months: M25-M48. WP Leader: 27-ISS. WP Deputy Leader: I-ANSES

JIP4-WP4-T1: Collection of the Laboratory Protocols for Model Organisms

Description of the task: Collection of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of selected foodborne pathogens, including STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, in use in the EU/EEA laboratories. The collection will include; 1) Acquire an overview of the methods adopted for the detection, characterisation and typing of the selected pathogens. 2) Compilation of information about the methodologies applied for the detection of the selected pathogens and for AMR. Notably, the laboratories enrolled, in this collection, will be the NRLs for *each* specific organism as defined by EFSA and ECDC. The collection will be administered by the OHEJP partner institutes. Information on the methodologies applied in the networks of National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) for *E. coli* and Parasites, nominated according to EU Regulation 625/2017 in the Veterinary field, will also be shared. Proprietary methods, certified by a third party (such as Nordval: <https://www.nmkl.org/index.php/nb/nordval>, Microval: <https://microval.org/>, AFNOR: the French standardization organization) in accordance with the protocol set out in EN/ ISO standard 16140 or other internationally accepted similar protocols will also be considered. Additional Laboratories working in Public Health sector participating in the ECDC Proficiency Testing schemes may also be enrolled.

Progress: The collection of protocols applied for the detection and typing of the selected microorganisms, namely Shiga Toxin Producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, was addressed to laboratories operating in both the Public Health and Veterinary/Food Safety areas. Laboratories of different Networks were reached and these included: OH-Harmony-CAP partners, NRLs coordinated by EURLs for *E. coli*, Parasites and AMR, as well as Public Health Laboratories of the ECDC Food and Waterborne Diseases (FWD) Network. The collection of protocols formally ended in M33 and the documents received included Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), Book chapters, PhD Thesis, papers, National standards for Microbiology investigation, EFSA and ECDC documents or general description of the protocols in use.

Overall 23 Institutions operating in Public Health or Veterinary and Food Safety field, either participants of the OH-Harmony-CAP project or from other networks responded to our request. The protocols/documents shared consist in:

- 49 protocols on STEC
- 6 protocols on ETEC
- 7 documents on both ETEC/STEC
- 20 protocols on *Cryptosporidium*
- 17 protocols on AMR in *Salmonella* and/or *Campylobacter*
- 2 documents providing information on the detection and typing of STEC, *Cryptosporidium*, AMR *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

- 1 document on *Cryptosporidium*, AMR *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

Related to the AMR task, it was agreed on a Project meeting held in M35 to include EUCAST documents.

JIP4-WP4-T2: Evaluation of the Collected Laboratory Protocols

Task Leader: 41-SVA

Progress: The task on the evaluation of the protocols collected was initiated as scheduled and is ongoing. Three groups consisting each of about four or five experts in pathogenic *E. coli*, *Cryptosporidium* and AMR, participating in OH-Harmony-CAP project, have been formed, with the aim of facilitating the comparison of the procedures collected in the framework of task 4.1. To do so, evaluation tables have been deployed by task 4.2 leaders and agreed within the groups of experts, to aid the primary assessment of the protocols, to be shared at a later stage with the whole WP4 participant

6.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

6.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1	Preliminary data management plan	M33	M36			This report is publically available https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-Harmony-Cap	8
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.1	Completed pilot survey	M36	M36			This report is publically available https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-Harmony-Cap	1
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.2	Technical Report of the Pilot Survey Results	M36		M38			2,4,6
OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.1	Technical report on the current and best practice in sampling	M36	M36			This report is publically available https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=OH-Harmony-Cap	2,4,6

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

6.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1	Kick-off meeting completed	M25	Yes		This milestone has been completed
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2	WP3-T1-ST1 completed	M36	Yes		This milestone has been completed
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3	Preparing a list of methods for the detection, Characterisation and typing of the selected pathogens in the EU/EEA NRLs	M36	Yes		This milestone has been completed
OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.4	WP3-T1-ST2 completed	M36	Yes		This milestone has been completed

6.4. Publications and additional outputs

By the end of the first year of the project, no peer-reviewed publications were published.

Additional output

- Oral presentation at OHEJP CARE KOM Meeting, Denmark February 12th 2020
- Oral presentation at the Fifth cogwheel workshop between OHEJP and JPIAMR, online April 28th 2020
- Oral presentation at OHEJPASM2020, online May 29th 2020

6.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

All draft reports were shared for comments with contact persons at ECDC and EFSA. The contact persons were also invited to online meetings of the project.

WP4 of OH-Harmony-Cap is examining unpublished sequences encoding Stx1 and Stx2 in STEC in order to establish possible new subtypes and variants, in collaboration with RKI, Germany, FDA, FSIS, CDC and NCBI, USE and with Health Canada. Moreover, the WP is developing databases with all relevant virulence genes from ETEC in collaboration with Swedish colleagues at the University of Gothenburg.

OH-Harmony-Cap collaborates with projects that have focus on the pathogens selected for the work, including OHEJP Projects PARADISE and TOXOSOURCES.

6.6. Data Management Plan

Have you uploaded a first version of the project's DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?

Yes

Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.

No

The Deliverable about the DMP is available at Zenodo. The final DMP will be published at the end of the project lifetime. The list of data covered in OH-Harmony-Cap DMP was specified during Y3. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. Also, the management of the data is discussed proactively and the DMP is regularly discussed with the OH-HARMONY-CAP-WP-leaders and with the OH-Harmony-Cap Consortium during the project.

The Deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.1.1 has the general description of the DMP. The DMP itself is compiled using a specific tool provided by the OHEJP: Collaborative Data Platform (CDP). Due to the delayed access to the tool, the first version of the DMP was finished with minor delay, M33.

6.7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of ethical reviewers in 2020	What measures and actions do you propose?	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020	Comments Project Leaders, January 2021	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2021	Comments Project Leaders, January 2022
(1) Health and Safety: On the ethics checklist you have ticked a safety issue, therefore the beneficiaries must confirm that appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.	None received, none implemented	Assume this means there is no response from the researchers, please remind the team a response is needed (Reply to be clarified, what does 'none received' mean?)	Apologies for the unclear answer. We meant that no specific issues had been identified. The laboratories are used to working with the pathogens included in the work. Appropriate health and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in the project.		
(2) Other – dual-use: On the ethics checklist you have ticked that this research involves some “dual-use items in the sense of Regulations 428/2009, or other items for which an authorisation is required”, therefore please provide a risk assessment and details on measures to prevent misuse of research findings must be provided.	Not relevant at present as no “dual-use items” were exchanged nor cultured.	N/A			

6.8. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	Yes

Additional information

Since the planning of the project, the OH-Harmony-Cap group has proactively identified, assessed, responded, and managed key dependencies and risks.

Selected Key Risk	Mitigation
COVID-19 pandemic	Flexible workplan to work around any delays
Low workshop in-person attendance	E-learning
Low response to the adjusted survey	Proactive email and other communications
Unclear survey questions	Mini pilots and quality control prior to launch
Loss of key staff	Deputies nominated for all key tasks, group work

6.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	OHEJP CARE KOM Meeting		
Date:	February 12 th 2020		
Place:	Technical University of Denmark		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Fifth cogwheel workshop between OHEJP and JPIAMR		
Date:	April 28 th 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	Yes
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM 2020		
Date:	May 29 th 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	10
Industry	10	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	100	Other	
Policy Makers	50		

7. JIP5 - MATRIX

7.1. Summary of the work carried out

The MATRIX project aims to advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice by building onto existing resources, adding value to them and creating synergies among the sectors at a national level. One of the founding pillars of MATRIX is the knowledge that each country has different infrastructural and economic realities with respect to setting up functional OHS, and all MATRIX outputs will take into consideration these different realities.

The project officially launched on January 1st 2020. A physical full consortium meeting was held in February in Lisbon, Portugal, where all partner institutes were represented and 39 individuals participated in the scheduled sessions.

In the kick-off meeting, each of the six work packages (WPs) within MATRIX presented their plans for the coming year. During two parallel sessions, the WPs agreed on several important steps to coordinate work between WPs and existing OHEJP projects – primarily to avoid overlap and duplication of work. Despite the extension of many first-call OHEJP Project deadlines, MATRIX members were able to attend an ORION and COHESIVE special workshop during the year that provided an overview of the status of the projects. Internally, WPs with similar tasks (WP1 & WP2 and WP4 & WP5 in particular) decided to collaborate closely.

The project met with a few challenges during the first year, including, the Project leadership changing hands in April, but remained at the same institute, SSI. At the same time, COVID-19 was being identified as a pandemic and increasingly demanding the attention of all workers in health related activities.

The sudden and severe emergence of COVID-19 has had a significant impact on work in all OH sectors across Europe including the planned progress within MATRIX, especially during the first 6 months. MATRIX was forced to end the planned collaboration with St. Kitts to test the roadmap. Within the project, some meetings were cancelled and/or moved to an online format, new personnel were not able to be hired, causing some disruptions in the ability to begin work within MATRIX, even forcing one institute to withdraw entirely from the project. As such, delays in some tasks were unavoidable. However, many institutes were able to continue after a short delay and as a result of the pandemic may have even strengthened national level communications by creating an opportunity for laboratories and epidemiologists from the animal health (AH) and food safety (FS) sectors to help support the epidemic control work carried by the public health (PH) institutes in their country.

Following the COVID delay; on June 4th 2020, the coordination team held the first consortium-wide meeting since the kick-off meeting. During the meeting, timelines were readjusted as a result of the resource re-allocation during the pandemic and the 1st call project extensions. One deliverable in WP2 and one deliverable in WP4 were delayed until Y4 but the other deliverables in Y3 were completed as expected, and no other delays are expected. However, MATRIX work picked up during the second half of the year: an additional consortium-wide meeting and two WP leader specific meetings were completed during the year.

WP1 was able to assist with, then agree to assume responsibility for the future continuation of, collecting and creating an inventory of current surveillance frameworks developed in ORION. WP1 will be able to seamlessly continue the aims of the ORION WP and continue to add value to this framework. WP1 has written a report (deliverable D-WP1.1) based on knowledge gained through the process of developing the questionnaires and analysis of the received data. This report describes the commonalities and differences between the individual surveillance components across sectors. The report was uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX website and will be uploaded to Zenodo when additional data is received over the next few months.

WP2 was able to develop three online questionnaires focused on a specific hazard and food production chain, one per each involved sector for a total of twelve questionnaires. These were disseminated to experts in late November and answers were collected in December, with analysis to begin in January. Data from these questionnaires will be used for mapping surveillance chains and the ability for institutions to share surveillance methods across animal, human and food systems.

WP3 mainly focused on conducting a literature review of output based surveillance studies. More activities are planned in the second half of the project.

In the fourth WP, a preliminary comparative analysis of the criteria used in some of previously developed tools (ECOSUR, NEOH, and RISKSUR) was conducted to characterise the overlap and differences between those tools. This comparison aimed to identify a limited set of strategic criteria, to be included in EU-EpiCap tool, regarding governance and organisation of multi-sectoral collaborations, technical characteristics of the collaboration, functional characteristics, surveillance short and intermediate-term outcomes. The review is planned for M39.

For WP5, the requirement analysis for the OH surveillance roadmap (JIP5-WP5-T1) was delayed in starting but initial data collection has begun and the analysis of resources from other EJP projects started. In addition, the collection of requirements for the technical infrastructure of the Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) was performed and it was decided to extend the OHS Codex developed by ORION. Developing this platform will link project outcomes and resources (e.g., tools/technologies/features) as well as support knowledge exchange between different MATRIX partners and stakeholders.

Facilitating the development of dashboards that enable data-driven surveillance to be carried out as an inter-sectorial activity, at the national level is the work of WP6. The work thus far has been restricted to WP leader (Sweden) and co-leader (Norway) agencies within their countries and generalization to other countries will be the goal of the next months of this task. Focus will be given to cementing achievements of previous projects, such as the dashboards developed in OHEJP-NOVA and the open data publishing routines created in OHEJP-ORION.

7.2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Existing frameworks and OH capacity

The aim of WP1 is to provide the foundation for adapting existing AH, PH, and FS surveillance frameworks into systems that can support cross-sectorial surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards.

Existing surveillance systems from the separate sectors, AH, PH and FS were generally developed mutual exclusivity. Therefore, they often collect data on different variables, in different formats, using different sampling strategies and so on. This lack of harmonization means that it can be difficult to integrate and use data from the multiple different sectors. To begin developing common frameworks for designing and implementing surveillance and control activities, it was necessary to identify, describe and analyse the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in AH, PH and FS. This work could be done from two angles; the first was to look at commonalities and differences between sector specific surveillance systems for individual zoonotic or food borne pathogens (individual components), and the second was to look at commonalities and differences in existing One Health Surveillance approaches for individual pathogens that span the sectors (multisector components). These data can then be used to both determine where harmonization can occur across the surveillance spectrum and secondly to identify what currently works and what does not to inform development of a best practice One Health model framework.

JIP05-WP1-T1: Generate an inventory of existing frameworks for surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards, by sector (AH, PH, and FS)

To identify and describe the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in AH, PH and FS, at the level of the individual components, we collaborated with the Orion project within OHEJP in developing and populating an inventory of surveillance systems across the AH, PH and FS sectors for each project member's country. We then used our experiences from assisting with the development process and analysis of the final data to address the question of commonalities and differences.

The development process, driven by ORION, was as follows. In the first step, an exhaustive list of potential variables and input options (where suitable) for the inventories was created and organized into logical categories. Variables requesting confidential data were not considered. Consensus selection occurred over several rounds of consultation within the ORION consortium, EFSA and ECDC. The final list of variables for PH, AH and FS were mapped against variables already collected by ECDC and EFSA to minimise duplication.

Extensive discussion and consultation amongst project members, EFSA and ECDC highlighted that three separate questionnaires were needed (one for each sector) to appropriately capture the data of interest. This went against the initial plan to capture data from all three sectors in a single questionnaire, but was necessary to keep the questionnaires simple yet accommodate unresolvable differences.

Questionnaires were designed in Excel and variables arranged and grouped by category. Entry options for closed question variables were not restricted and free-text was enabled, however, a message encouraged participants to use the drop-down options where possible. A guide was provided with the Excel questionnaire, explaining each variable, the associated question, the data type required and whether it was a mandatory or optional variable.

The Excel questionnaires and associated guides were distributed to all members of Orion WP2 and Matrix members by e-mail. Responses were saved in raw format on the Friedrich Loeffler Institute server in a restricted access folder and collated in a single separate Master-version for each questionnaire type. Final data were uploaded to a public platform, 'One Health EJP Inventory' that was developed within the Orion project specifically to facilitate public access to the data. The platform can be accessed at <https://shiny.fli.de/home/>

This public platform, and therefore all the collated data, is available to all MATRIX members and will provide the basis for comparisons between the different surveillance components.

A report (D-WP1.1) is currently uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX website and is in review before publication on Zenodo that describes the commonalities and differences between the individual surveillance components across the sectors. This report is based on knowledge gained through the process of developing the questionnaires and analysis of the received data. The report was completed and available to Matrix members by 04 January 2021.

WP2: Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration

During spring 2020, the epidemiological situation regarding COVID-19 in Italy was of particular concern and the WP2 lead, IZSAM, was involved in many activities in response to the outbreak. For this reason, there were some difficulties in meeting agreed upon deadlines decided at the kick-off meeting in Lisbon. However, WP2 started to collect information and outputs from other EJP projects, such as NOVA, ORION and COHESIVE. A new "project"-file was created within the MATRIX closed group at onehealthjip.eu named "WP2 Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration" used to share documents between WP2 members.

JIP5-WP2-T1: Mapping of the surveillance chain across all sectors for each hazard-track

During the kick-off meeting, it was agreed that this WP could make good use of the ORION surveillance inventory (ORION WP2 Epi) to identify cross-sectorial frameworks that are already in place or could be used for a full OHS. This WP will not include individual projects (such as temporary local surveillance projects) unless there is scope within these for large-scale coverage or important new knowledge.

WP2 is working on the mapping of the surveillance chain across sectors through country-based case studies, each of which basing on one hazard track and one production chain, as a specific “country-hazard-production”. Four hazard-food production chain combinations were selected: *Salmonella* and pork meat food chain; *Listeria* and dairy products; *Campylobacter* and poultry meat food chain; Hepatitis E and wild boar meat food chain. For every combination, at least two country case studies are foreseen. To collect information about the surveillance in place for the selected combinations and countries, WP2 developed three online questionnaires per hazard-food production chain, one per each involved sector for a total of twelve questionnaires. Online questionnaires have been disseminated to experts in late November. Answers were gathered through mid-December.

While this WP was waiting for preliminary results from WP1 on the inventory of existing surveillance frameworks to complete the assessment of the additional information to be collected, the leaders of Task 1 collaborated with the leaders of WP2 Task 2 for agreements on deliverable sharing and templates.

JIP5-WP2-T2: Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, particularly, which outputs should be shared and how they should be shared for OH orientated decision making

As the results of the questionnaires implemented for WP2-T1 are collected, WP2 is starting to work on the identification of linkages between the surveillance activities performed by the different sectors and the main outputs already available that could be shared to both implement OH surveillance and orientate decision-making processes.

The deliverable associated with Task 1 and Task 2 was postponed to M42, due to the COVID impact on the ability to begin these tasks.

JIP5-Task: WP2-T3: Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis, and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial OH collaboration, for each specific hazard-track.

During the last months of 2020, WP2 started to gather the conclusions from the first round of OHEJP projects, in particular from COHESIVE and NOVA. However, some of the documents are not yet available since the end of first round of OHEJP projects was extended due the COVID-19 pandemic.

WP3: Output-based surveillance evaluation

WP3 aims to review and build upon work in EJP projects and previous European funded projects to look at the practicalities of implementing output-based surveillance within a one-health context. Unfortunately, the WP has been heavily impacted by the loss of key personnel. During March, one of the task leaders and major contributor to this WP had to withdraw from the consortium due to COVID-19. In November, the leader of the WP announced that she will be leaving the consortium and is in the process of looking for a replacement.

While progress has slowed due to the COVID situation and the loss of a partner (UCM-Visavet), this WP organized a teleconference meeting this spring, and the WP leaders are working to redistribute the tasks of this former partner. It is anticipated that the tasks will be redistributed and/or re-planned without compromising the quality of expected deliverables. Attempts are being made to reallocate UCM’s budget, some of this has been reallocated to an existing partner to allow greater involvement in one of the WP 3 tasks on surveillance system evaluation. The WP 3 package was originally planned to have ‘light’ activities in the first half of the project with the majority of activity being in 2021/22.

JIP5-WP3-T1: Inventory of previous work and current practice

Currently working on a literature search of papers relevant to the topic of output based surveillance. One emergency meeting was conducted to address the withdrawal of one of the partners. Plans for hosting meetings (teleconferences) every two months was delayed by the WP3 leader since her immediate obligations were assigned to COVID-19 duties. Progress on MATRIX activities was reprioritized around June.

Several of the partners have completed internal inventories of methodologies or ongoing work that complimentary to the work package in the area of case-finding and evaluation of existing surveillance systems for Antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

JIP5-WP3-T2: Identification of operational partners and stakeholders

The collation of the stakeholder mapping exercise has been delayed due to COVID and Avian Influenza (the work package is dominated by animal health partners), however it was originally planned as an ongoing task through the project and the delay should not affect the outcome. The WP plans to use RISKSUR as input and use the information gathered in the SIGMA project for stakeholder mapping. The WP plans to set up a case study in year two, focusing on a topic of significant relevance to most of the EU region.

WP4: EUEpiCap

In WP4, a generic benchmarking tool (EU-EpiCap) for characterizing, monitoring and evaluating surveillance capacities, which directly contribute to OH surveillance, is being developed. The tool aims to identify and describe the collaborations among actors involved in the surveillance of a pathogen/hazard of the food chain and to characterise (with a set of indicators) the One Health-ness (OH-ness) of the surveillance system.

The development of the tool will be based on a semi-quantitative approach to characterise the profile of EU countries (at least of the countries involved in MATRIX) regarding the OH-ness of surveillance for some of the hazards belonging to the different MATRIX hazard tracks (i.e. *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *Listeria*, and emerging threats). The evaluation will take into account contextual variables, such as the importance of the hazard in the country.

The tool will allow advising better implementation of existing OHS initiatives and expand OHS across similar contexts, in collaboration with WP5. WP4 and WP5 keep strong collaboration and synergy; a web meeting to coordinate the work in WP4 and WP5 was held on 28th February 2020. Coordination with other multi-sectorial activities such as the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SIS OT) are also taking place.

JIP5-WP4-T1: Review of existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation

An inventory of existing methods of evaluation of surveillance systems, including both methods of evaluation of surveillance functioning and methods of evaluation of multi-sectoral collaborations, was conducted. A large array of tools and guides was identified:

- animal health surveillance evaluation framework (SERVAL) [1],
- assessment tool of epidemiological surveillance systems in animal health and food safety [outil d'analyse des systèmes de surveillance] (OASIS) [2],
- evaluation of collaboration for surveillance (ECoSur) [3],
- FAO assessment tool for laboratory and AMR surveillance systems (ATLASS),
- FAO progressive management pathway (PMP-AMR) for Antimicrobial Resistance,
- FAO surveillance evaluation tool (SET),
- IHR joint external evaluation (JEE) [4],
- network for evaluation of one health (NEOH) [5],

- one health assessment for planning and performance (OH-APP),
- one health systems mapping and analysis resource toolkit (OH-SMART) [6],
- RISKSUR surveillance evaluation tool (SURVTOOL) [7],
- surveillance and information sharing operational tool (SIS OT),
- surveillance evaluation framework (SurF) [8],
- Integrated surveillance system evaluation project (ISSEP) [9].

In order to become familiarized with those tools, the objectives, assessment type (qualitative, semi-quantitative, etc.) and functioning (including a description of the criteria, scoring system and outputs of each tool) were reviewed. Previous literature reviews assessing the strengths and weaknesses of those tools and providing guidance on how to choose a fit-for-purpose tool were also consulted [10-12](<https://guidance.fp7-risksur.eu/>).

MATRIX aims to propose a EU-EpiCap tool that is generic and user friendly, to be implemented easily and regularly in European countries on a large range of foodborne (and ideally other health-related) hazards to provide a map of key epidemiology services and one health capacities and capabilities for surveillance. When previous evaluations have been conducted, the EU-EpiCap tool will be filled as much as possible using results from these. A connection with ECDC partners involved in the development of the EU-LabCap (a similar tool assessing the capacity and capabilities for European of microbiology laboratories to provide essential public health functions) was established, allowing EU-EpiCap to build on previous experience from Eu-LabCap (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/eu-laboratory-capability-monitoring-system-eulabcap-report-2016-survey-eueea>)

A preliminary comparative analysis of the criteria used in some of these tools (ECOSUR, NEOH, and RISKSUR) was conducted in order to characterise the overlap and differences between those tools. This comparison aimed to identify a limited set of strategic criteria, to be included in EU-EpiCap tool, regarding governance and organisation of multi-sectoral collaborations, technical characteristics of the collaboration, functional characteristics, surveillance short and intermediate-term outcomes. Each step of surveillance (planning, data collection, data sharing, data analysis, result dissemination, etc.) are being considered. Additionally, connections were made with FAO partners in charge of developing the ATLASS and PMP-AMR tools (both tools require FAO training before they can be used/accessed to), and the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT) being developed between FAO, OIE and WHO.

A literature search was conducted to identify case studies of application of those methods for each food safety hazard targeted in MATRIX and for other hazards. MATRIX consortium partners were solicited for additional, unpublished, case studies in their countries. Applications were found for several tools on AMR: OASIS [13], ECOSUR [14], NEOH [12, 15], AMR-PMP [12], RISKSUR ([13], 29), ATLASS and SURVTOOL (<https://guidance.fp7-risksur.eu/>) and *Salmonella* (unpublished results of OASIS and ECOSUR evaluations in France), but no application of those evaluation methods were found for *Campylobacter* and *Listeria*. In order to identify additional case studies, some questions regarding previous evaluations of surveillance systems were included in the questionnaires implemented in WP2 about surveillance of hazards in animal health, food chain and human health sectors. In addition, some data on existing surveillance systems may be collected from ORION.

A research associate was recruited by the University of Surrey (Deputy WP4) and another recruitment occurred on Dec 14th 2020 at ANSES (Lead WP4). Both recruits will be working part time on MATRIX. In preparation of the second task of WP4 (Development of a surveillance capacity tool), the research associate based at Surrey attended a training on “Introduction to R Shiny” (to build web applications).

The deliverable on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities was reported to March 2021 (instead of December 2020, initially).

WP5 Outreach and roadmap

WP5 has two major tasks. First, it will produce a roadmap for developing and implementing national OHS activities targeted at different capacity levels. The second major task is the implementation of a Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) that supports knowledge exchange between different MATRIX partners with close connection to the overarching EJP platform. This platform will offer resources (e.g., tools/technologies/features) that support collaborative collection, exchange, management and creation of knowledge. The KIP will further facilitate the dissemination and permanent access to the generated project outcomes from all MATRIX WPs. This task will also make sure to re-use/build upon relevant outputs from EJP projects like ORION and COHESIVE.

JIP5-WP5-T1: Perform a requirement analysis for national OH surveillance roadmaps

- This task shows high potential for synergies with WP4. Therefore, a strong collaboration between both WPs was agreed. To coordinate this, a WP4-WP5-web meeting took place on 28th February 2020. In addition, it is agreed that WP4 and WP5 members can participate in WP-specific meetings. This began in the WP4 meeting in July 2020, where a member of WP5 actively participated.
- The planning on the execution of the requirement analysis for the national OH surveillance roadmaps have begun.
- First activities within this tasks:
 - The analysis of resources from other EJP projects, like COHESIVE and NOVA, started.
 - An initial search was conducted gathering examples of roadmaps from various fields (i.e., product development and project management).

JIP5-WP5-T2: Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap template

This task will start in Y4. An initial meeting was conducted in December between Task 1 and Task 2.

JIP5-WP5-T3: Knowledge-Integration Platform

- The requirement analysis for the Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) was performed. The technical resources from other EJP projects, ORION and RADAR, were analysed. In addition, the collection of requirements for the technical infrastructure of the KIP was performed.
- It was decided that the KIP should support the following aspects:
 1. Exchange of mathematical models from different OH sectors. To accomplish that, it will be necessary that the dedicated KIP section supports harmonized information exchange formats, e.g., the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format (former FSK-ML, see <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-ml-food-safety-knowledge-markup-language/>). The extension of the FSKX format towards PH/OH started. For that, web meetings that deal with FSKX format with members of the RADAR project and the RAKIP initiative (who maintains FSKX format) were conducted. Re-implementation of existing OH risk models as FSKX compliant files started with the purpose of validating the proposed PH/OH FSKX extension. Dedicated meetings that dealt with technical questions of example source-attribution models took place with domain experts.
 2. Knowledge on uncertainty assessments. For this BfR performed an internal pilot study that will create a national, BfR-internal platform on uncertainty assessments. The lessons learned in that pilot will affect the KIP development.
 3. Supporting the WHO/OIE/FAO Tripartite Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit (SISOT)–for this WP5 members participated in several SISOT web meetings to find potential synergies and to align the work of WP5 with the WHO/OIE/FAO team.

- The development of the KIP started. First, the technical infrastructure was chosen; it was decided to extend the OHS Codex that was developed in the ORION project. The OHS Codex is a high-level framework that supports mutual understanding and knowledge exchange. This resource is publicly available as a readthedocs-web page (<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>). Consequently, the KIP is available as the same readthedocs-web page. To extend the OHS Codex, it is planned to add relevant resources and, if needed, extend the OHS Codex framework. The collection of resources that should be added to the OHS Codex started.
- A close collaboration between MATRIX and ORION was established, i.e., members of MATRIX participate regularly in relevant ORION calls.

JIP5-WP5-T4: Training and dissemination

MATRIX-internal resources

- Video to inform the MATRIX community on demand about the OHS Codex, which is the basis for the KIP

Dissemination events

- Presentation about MATRIX on the Cogwheel workshop (28th April 2020)
- Presentation about Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) Format (FSK-ML) and its extension towards OH on the Annual Scientific Meeting (27th-29th May 2020)
- Poster presentation about the exchange format FSK-ML on World One Health Congress (30th October-3rd November 2020)
- Dissemination and training event for the national, BfR-internal platform that facilitates exchange knowledge on uncertainty assessments (6th November 2020)
- Presentation about MATRIX on the Cogwheel workshop (25th November 2020)

WP6: Decision and collaboration dashboards

JIP05-WP6-T1: Country-based Identification of existing cross-sectional OH's activities

This WP will create dashboards of OHS inputs and outputs, highlighting possible pitfalls and biases in multi-sectorial data analysis. Apart from data analysis and interpretation, the dashboards will also indicate which persons to contact in a specific situation such as an outbreak of a zoonotic disease. The WP will build on knowledge from particularly NOVA and COHESIVE and will ensure that synergies are created with the COHESIVE dashboards in order to avoid overlap. At the kick-off meeting, it was agreed that the partners in the WP would communicate primarily via emails, focusing on sharing ideas, and during the second physical consortium meeting, planned for the Fall 2020, the group would revise the ideas and trace a strategy for the work during the rest of the year. Besides the cancellation of the physical meeting, the COVID-19 pandemic affected the start of this task significantly due to the large expected involvement of public health authorities, as the dashboards are meant to be a One-Health activity. National level coordination between animal and public health authorities were carried out in Sweden and Norway (WP leaders and co-leaders) to discuss the country needs. However, the extension of the discussion to other project members has been postponed to 2021.

JIP05-WP6-T2: Defining the content needs for cross-sectoral decision and collaboration dashboards

As stated above, this exercise has been started, as planned in the submitted work plan, during the fall of 2020. However, the work so far has been restricted to WP leader (Sweden) and co-leader (Norway) agencies within their countries, and generalization to other countries will be the goal of the next

months of this task (planned to last up to month 54). Focus will be given to cementing achievements of previous projects, such as the dashboards developed in OHEJP-NOVA and the open data publishing routines created in OHEJP-ORION.

WP0: Coordination

At all meetings, all participants were specifically informed about the dissemination strategy and reminded that deliverables are considered public unless an explicit request is made to make it private. Regarding general coordination of the project, it was agreed that:

- **Teleconferences.** The coordination team will not provide any specific platform for web-meetings, and each WP leader should use the resources made available by their own institutes to host WP meetings. Each WP leader is responsible for arranging WP meetings when necessary. The MATRIX coordination team will host consortium and coordination meetings using SVA's license for Adobe Connect. WP leaders wanting to host public seminars or record sessions for public distribution using Adobe Connect should contact SVA to arrange.

- **File sharing.** The MATRIX closed group will be based at the onehealthejp.eu website. However, because it is difficult to organize files here, this platform will not be used to share working files. Each WP leader is expected to manage file sharing according to their own needs and institutional resources. The MATRIX group at the OHEJP website will be used only to upload final documents (e.g. meeting minutes and deliverables).

- **Meeting minutes.** The coordination team has created an online file to document all meetings, using the same file with the latest minutes on top. This allows all members to find all resources and links in one place.

- **Other resources.** The coordination has created an online Google documents page with a link to all relevant resources as well as an updated address/contact list for all WP leaders and the whole consortium. It was agreed that participants are responsible for updating their contact information (including adding new members or removing others from their institution). All WP leaders need to use the latest contact list version. The coordination team will not keep track of the participation in the different WPs and institutions can change WP participation as necessary, making sure to keep the WP leaders informed. All relevant documents will also be added to the FORUM space on the MATRIX homepage at the OHEJP website. The presentations and minutes from the kick-off meeting were shared with the consortium on the Google documents page.

- **Data management plan.** The coordination team assumed the responsibilities of managing the Data Management Plan and uploaded a draft onto the approved program on October 31st. The deliverable associated with this draft was completed and uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX webpage and Zenodo (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471349>) with a minor delay in M37.

Other Consortium-wide meetings were conducted in June and October 2020. Due to the significant impact of personal and institutional capabilities to work on MATRIX activities during the COVID pandemic, the goals of these meetings were to meet, check in to see any progress, plan and adjust goals, and take the time to get all partners focused on MATRIX activities.

Between the consortium-wide meetings during July and November 2020 (approximately every 6 weeks), a WP and Hazard Track leader meeting have been conducted.

Hazard Tracks (MATRIX-specific organizational group)

The hazard tracks, which are a signature feature of MATRIX, will ensure that work in all WPs is directly relevant to specific pathogens/hazards. The tracks as follows were chosen based on institution work priorities and OH impact relevance: (1) *Campylobacter*, (2) *Salmonella* (3) *Listeria* and (4) Emerging threats. During the kick-off meeting, it was highlighted that not all WPs will have work that is focused on track-specific outputs and therefore do not have to deliver work relevant to all tracks. The

consortium agreed that it was not necessary to increase the number of tracks, as it is not guaranteed that work can be delivered for more than four tracks.

The Emerging Threats track was highlighted in the consortium-wide meetings. It was discussed whether this encompasses a general preparedness against emerging threats or a focus on specific new emerging pathogens. The consortium agreed that each WP might choose one of the above scopes, according to the specific contents of the WP and the interests of the WP participants. The two main topics of Antimicrobial resistance and Hepatitis E have emerged as the topics of importance to the participants.

7.3. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

7.3.1. Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Is this delay due to COVID-19?	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
MATRIX	D-WP0.1	Data Management Plan - draft	M36	M34			The Draft was created on Oct 31. Reviews were received by 04 January 2021. The report was written and uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX webpage and Zenodo at http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471349 in M37. The DMP will be continuously updated at a minimum of every three months.	3
MATRIX	D-WP1.1	Report on the commonalities and differences of the different operational frameworks in AH, PH, and FS	M36	M36			Uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX site on January 4. Undergoing validation and review prior to publishing on Zenodo. This will be uploaded by 01 March 2021	1
MATRIX	D-WP2.1	Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages	M42					1
MATRIX	D-WP4.1	Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities.	M39					4

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

7.3.2. Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
MATRIX	M-WP3.1	End of the first round of OHEJP projects: this will coincide with the end of the inventory and requirement analysis phase in most WPs	M36	No	M42	The end of the first round of OHEJP Projects was extended due to Coronavirus. Therefore, our inventory and requirement analysis will attempt to obtain the resources from the projects directly instead of relying on the publicly available expected outcomes.

7.4. Publications and additional outputs

We do not have any peer-reviewed or other publications at this time.

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)

Additional output

None at this time

7.5. On-going and planned collaborations with national or European projects or networks

Several MATRIX members are also members of ORION, and will be able to transfer results and add value to them within MATRIX. WP1 leaders in MATRIX are also leaders of the work package on epidemiological knowledge sharing in OH in the ORION project. Leaders of MATRIX WP5 and WP6 are part of an initiative in ORION – called “supra-national One-health pilot” that is working closely with EFSA and ECDC to determine how the OH tools developed in ORION can be applied to the European Union level. We expect that work to benefit directly the roadmap and outreach work that we will develop in MATRIX’s WP5.

WP1 is working closely together with WP2 of ORION, where FLI is also actively involved. At a national level, collaborations were continued with BfR (National institute for Risk assessment – Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung - <https://www.bfr.bund.de/en>) as well. Furthermore, the FLI is engaged in different working groups and projects with EFSA, working on surveillance and different animal diseases and EFSA regarding their terminology and inventory variables.

WP2 leaders in MATRIX are also leaders of the COHESIVE work package 4 on data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control in this project and deputy leaders of task 2.1 about availability of food purchase data and barriers of the NOVA project WP2. The WP is also collaborating with the project BeONE in the evaluation and implementation of national level data sharing (WP3) as lead and deputy lead on several tasks. In addition, national-level collaborations were developed in France with surveillance actors; French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety: national reference laboratories on *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, and Santé Publique France, the National Public Health Agency.

In addition, WP2 leader (IZSAM) is the coordinator of the SIGMA Consortium, a project funded by the EFSA, which aims at finding solutions for facilitating the exchange of data between Member States and EFSA. Although the SIGMA project is limited to animal health issues, the data mapping solutions and the tools under development in this project can be of interest for MATRIX, as possible approaches applicable also in food safety.

The WP3 leader is also closely involved in COHESIVE WP2 (development of OH implementation guide) and COHESIVE WP3 (sharing of OH signals within and between countries) and is able to provide a point of contact to all the WP leaders in COHESIVE. Discussions have already taken place regarding having a webinar to discuss the COHESIVE WP outputs developed up to this point.

In the framework of the WP4, national-level collaborations were developed in France with the Food chain surveillance platform (website, in French: <https://www.plateforme-sca.fr/>; description of platform objectives and organisation, in English: https://www.plateforme-esa.fr/sites/default/files/documents/communication/Plaque%20de%20pr%C3%A9sentation_3_ptfs_29_01_2020_EN_nouveaux%20logos.pdf), especially the research group on *Salmonella* surveillance. International collaborations were identified with ECDC regarding the EU-LabCap tool and with FAO regarding the SISOT tool.

WP5 is collaborating extensively with other projects. WP5 members participated in the annual meeting of COHESIVE to determine synergies and identify possibly continued COHESIVE tasks. The extension of the FSKX format planned in WP5 is also relevant for the EJP RADAR project. In the RADAR project, a

model repository was developed that is already based on the FSKX format. We are in close communication with the responsible partners. In Task JIP5-WP5-T3, models compliant to the FSKX format are implemented. Mathematical models and their exchange are relevant in multiple other EJP projects, e.g., EJP DiSCoVer and CARE. We are planning a meeting regarding this topic. The development of FSKX format and the including metadata schema to annotate knowledge started within the research project “Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platforms (RAKIP)”. The RAKIP community, with partners from ANSES, DTU Food, and BfR, continues the collaboration to improve and extent the community-driven metadata schema. The work done in WP5 shows high potential for synergies with the work of the WHO/OIE/FAO SISOT-team (Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit). We are in close contact with the team to align the work and potentially identify reciprocally beneficial tasks. Based on the presentation held at the Cogwheel workshop in November 2020, the SafeConsume community indicated interest in learning more about the KIP and potentially using it. A discussion between MATRIX, ORION, and SafeConsume started.

WP6 deals with the creation of “data for decision dashboards”. The WP is collaborating with a similar WP in the OHEJP project BeONE.

7.6. Data Management Plan

1. *Have you uploaded a first version of the project’s DMP to the DMP group on the OHEJP website?*

The Data Management Plan leader attended the DMP training in September 2020 and obtained initial information of data from the WP leaders in October 2020. A draft was uploaded this data list to the DMP portal by October 31st, 2020. The DMP portal will be updated continuously throughout the Project at the minimal interval of every three months.

The deliverable D-W0.1 aim was to write an initial draft report of the DMP. It was completed and uploaded to the OHEJP-MATRIX webpage and Zenodo with minor delay in M37. It can be found here: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471349>

2. *Have you encountered any problems or difficulties when setting up and updating the DMP? If yes, please specify.*

There are some initial questions regarding the where and how our data should be listed. Integrative projects appear to have a more unusual set of data compared to Joint Research Projects. The DMP leader did receive feedback on the initial data entries at the end of December and was reviewing, editing and responding by January 2021.

7.7. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirements of ethical reviewers in 2020	What measures and actions do you propose?	Comments of Ethics Advisors, November 2020	Comments Project Leaders, January 2021	Comments of Ethics Advisors, October 2021	Comments Project Leaders, January 2022
(1) Non EU countries (Caribbean island of St. Kitts): On the ethics checklist you have not ticked non-EU countries, please edit and tick as the Caribbean island of St. Kitts. The beneficiaries must confirm that the research conducted outside the EU is in compliance with H2020 rules.	The Caribbean island of St. Kitts is intended to be provided a copy of the roadmap to utilize as an in country tool which will provide the roadmap proof of concept. However, they are not beneficiaries as they are not participating members of the project nor are they receiving any funding. Therefore, they were listed as “involved” but no potential ethic issues are raised.	N/A	As the pandemic rages on, and as our respective groups maintain some responsibilities to COVID-19 response activities. We decided it was in everyone’s interest to cancel this potential collaboration. Given the delay due to COVID and tight time frame and required capacity, neither partner could fulfil the intentions to perform a pilot in St Kitts on a road-mapping exercise developed by MATRIX. It is unfortunate to have to cancel, but both institutions decided it was best due to the situation. Therefore, we have decided that no information, documents, or any other material will be shared with St. Kitts		

			regarding MATRIX activities.		
(2) Personal data processing: The beneficiaries must confirm that no personal data will be collected as part of the project; otherwise the GDPR (EU 2016/679) must be applied and the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained must be provided.	St. Kitts will not be a beneficiary of any funding or participation in the work packages.	The beneficiaries do not provide the answer to the question raised previously in regard to the collection and processing of personal data as part of the project. If so, the beneficiaries must confirm that the GDPR (EU 2016/679) is applied and the contact address of the Data Protector Officer of the institution in charge of processing the data obtained must be provided. A response is required	As described in the Ethics Assessment of MATRIX full proposal (Annex 9), no personal data will be collected as part of MATRIX.		

7.8. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes *but not for final deadlines*
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes *but not for final deadlines*
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information

Our WP3 and *Salmonella* Hazard Track leader will be leaving the MATRIX Project by January 2021 and one of the task leaders within WP3 also left without being able to be replaced yet. Although the current WP leader is identifying a replacement, it is feared that this WP will face challenges in the remainder of the project. However, there is already one specific project planned and is moving forward within WP3, and there was not much planned activity for the WP3 in the first half of the project, so it may be able to recover without problem.

In March 2020, the increasing rates of novel coronavirus COVID-19 resulted in a general lock-down of many European countries and importantly a drastic need for all public health agencies to shift their work focus towards this disease and its impacts. The emergence of COVID-19, also affected the work undertaken in the veterinary and food safety sectors in Europe. As a result, some partner institutes in the MATRIX project have had delayed starts to tasks.

The following specific impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on MATRIX have already occurred:

- Minimal teleconferences or online meetings (consortium-wide or WP specific) were held between the kickoff meetings in February through early June.
- MATRIX personnel at several institutes were reassigned to work full time on COVID-19 and may have been unable to register the intended time to work on MATRIX. Possibly only able to register time for MATRIX intermittently during the first several months of the year. Recruitment of new MATRIX personnel was significantly delayed or indefinitely postponed for some partners. The allocated budgets may have been impacted for the year.
- The work in WP1 and WP2 to gather existing OHS information from other EJP projects by the end of April was prematurely halted, due to the OHEJP Project from the first call being granted an extension of their deliverables.
- The planned physical full consortium meeting in Teramo in October 2020 was canceled to follow travel restriction guidelines and social distancing recommendations. In addition, the planned physical full consortium meeting in Berlin in January 2021 has been postponed, with acknowledgment that the summer meeting planned in Norway may be cancelled as well.

The long-term specific impacts on the project are still unknown, but much recovery has occurring in the second half of 2020. Overall, it is expected that deliverables and milestones will be initially delayed, but we will make up time for most tasks along the project. Some tasks will be revised or their focus re-drawn, in particular in cases where partners were unable to hire new employees. Timelines will be assessed at regular intervals during the upcoming years.

Overall, the COVID situation appeared to delay the beginning of many tasks, but this amazing group has already made great strides in making up for lost time, and many tasks are on track to be completed after only a short pushback in the deliverable date.

7.9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Most of the following are recorded by E. M. Sundermann et al. (BfR)

Name of the activity:	Presentation at Cogwheel Workshop 5 with JPIAMR https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/74/files/20109/users/1602/download		
Date:	28 th April 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Presentation on Annual Scientific Meeting 2020 slides are available here: https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/74/files/20110/users/1602/download		
Date:	27 th -29 th May 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	180	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster at World One Health Congress https://onehealthejp.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/74/files/20932/users/1602/download		
Date:	30 th October- 3 rd November 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	
Industry	50	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	National, BfR-internal pilot		
Date:	6 th November 2020		
Place:	Berlin, Germany and online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	37	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Presentation Introduction on MATRIX Cogwheel Workshop 6 with SafeConsume https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-json/pm/v2/projects/74/files/20931/users/1602/download		
Date:	25 th November 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health Summer Course about One Health topics from the University of Copenhagen		
Date:	10 th -14 th August 2020		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /No		Yes /No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	40	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			